

Essentializing Reading Achievement of Key Stage 3 Learners Through Aral Program: Evidence-Based Reference

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ABSTRACT

The primary purpose of this research is to determine the relationship between the degree of the ARAL program implementation and the Key Stage 3 learners' reading achievement. The study utilized a quantitative-correlational research design using a standardized questionnaire. The study's locale was the secondary schools of Getafe 1 and 2 Districts, with 262 respondents. Complete confidentiality in the management and data disposal was adhered. The results revealed a significant positive relationship between the degree of ARAL Program implementation and learners' reading achievement. The findings further revealed that the learners' reading achievement improves as the ARAL program's implementation level increases. Moreover, it also indicated that the effectiveness of the program improves when the schools are adequately prepared for its implementation across five key domains such as Learners' Readiness, Tutors' Readiness, School Environment Readiness, Parental Readiness, and Support System and Governance Readiness. These results highlight the critical role of comprehensive program adoption, teacher readiness, school environment preparedness, parents' support and stakeholders' engagement in improving learners' reading skills.

KEYWORDS: *ARAL program implementation, reading achievement, Getafe 1 and 2 Districts, quantitative correlational research design, key stage 3 learners.*

1. RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Reading plays a critical role in learners' growth and development, as it serves as a fundamental building block for learning. According to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2023), literacy is a continuous process because beyond its traditional definition as a set of reading, writing, and counting skills, literacy is today viewed as a means of identifying, comprehending, interpreting, creating, and communicating in an increasingly digital, text-mediated, information-rich, and rapidly changing world. Literacy is a lifelong process of learning and proficiency in reading, writing, and using numbers, and it is part of a larger set of abilities that includes digital skills, media literacy, education for sustainable development, and global citizenship, as well as job-related skills.

In addition, significant advancements in literacy have been achieved, with the latest figures from the UNESCO Institute for Statistics indicating that over 86 percent of the global population is literate, compared to 68 percent in 1979. Nonetheless,

globally, at least 739 million adults remain illiterate (UIS, 2025), with two-thirds being women, and 250 million children are not attaining fundamental literacy abilities. Before the COVID-19 epidemic, which inflicted unprecedented disruption on schooling in a century, 617 million children and adolescents had not attained minimal reading proficiency.

The World Bank (2022) notes that reading is a key skill for learning throughout a child's education. Without strong reading skills, students have fewer chances to keep learning. Reading well also helps build a good foundation for other subjects. In low- and middle-income countries, more than half of students cannot read and understand a simple story by the end of primary school (Crawford et al., 2024). With this, the Philippine education system is now facing a serious learning crisis. The 2022 World Bank report, mentioned by the Second Congressional Commission on Education (EDCOM 2), found that the Philippines has one of the highest learning poverty rates in Asia at 90.9%. The country also

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ranked lowest in performance among ASEAN nations, except for Lao PDR (97.7%) and Brunei, which was not assessed. In other words, nine out of ten Filipino children aged 10 struggle to read and understand what they read.

According to the 2022 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results, the Philippines ranked in the bottom ten of 81 countries in reading comprehension, mathematics, and science for the second year in a row, with little improvement. After finishing last among 79 participating countries in reading comprehension in 2018, the Philippines ranked 76th out of 81 in 2022. The average reading score for 15-year-olds is 347 points, while the average score for OECD nations is 476 points. Indicators of the exam, however, revealed that while advancing in rank, the performance of top-performing students (TPS) in the country did not improve by percentage points, while low-performing students (LPS) had a 4.3 percent drop in reading comprehension. It only means that Filipino learners have inadequate reading achievement, which underscores the urgent need to create and strengthen literacy interventions and programs across all grade levels.

Additionally, during the COVID-19 pandemic, when face-to-face learning was disrupted for 2 years, it was observed that the reading proficiency of Filipino learners further declined. The sudden shift to modular, online, and blended learning limited opportunities to create meaningful, authentic learning experiences. This has caused significant learning gaps and losses in the Philippine education system, specifically in the learners' reading fluency and comprehension. (Felipe, 2022).

Recognizing the long-term impact of these learning losses, the Department of Education initiated the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program as an intervention to help learners cope with learning losses and improve literacy and numeracy skills. The goal of the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning Program is to enable students who perform below grade-level expectations in reading to catch up by offering them prompt, efficient, and responsive support.

The Department of Education institutionalizes the ARAL Program as a strategic, data-informed initiative to address learning disparities in literacy, mathematics, and science. Grounded in learning assessment data from the Comprehensive Rapid Literacy Assessment (CRLA), Rapid Mathematics Assessment (RMA), Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI), and other national tools, the ARAL Program aims to support learners who are

performing below grade level in reading, mathematics, and science. It guarantees that all Filipino learners receive expeditious, targeted, and equitable academic support. It seeks to ensure that by the conclusion of Grade 10, all students possess at least basic literacy skills (Department of Education, 2025).

In the Getafe 1 and 2 Districts, reading problems among Junior High School learners remain a significant issue, not just among primary school pupils. Teachers observed that many learners are still struggling to read and struggle with reading comprehension. Moreover, most of them can read the assigned materials, but it burdens them to understand the text and analyze its content critically (Tugo & Tabernilla, 2023). There could be several reasons for this problem, including differences in training, a lack of teaching materials, students' motivation to attend classes, or parents' lack of involvement in their children's academic achievement. So, it is crucial to understand how the ARAL Program is implemented in Getafe 2 District and how it affects students' reading abilities.

With this, the Department of Education requires the implementation of an ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASRRA), as outlined in Section M.87 of DO 18, s. 2025. The ASRRA is a structured, data-driven audit that assesses how prepared educational institutions are across five key areas: Learner Readiness, Teacher or Tutor Readiness, School Environment Readiness, Parental Readiness, and System Support Readiness.

The ASRRA is more than just a compliance requirement. It also helps map resources and identify where schools need more support, such as educational materials, learner support systems, and physical infrastructure. This approach ensures that program resources, such as local funding, tutorial support, program integration, psychosocial support, and remediation materials, are shared fairly. It also protects schools from pressure to implement programs without adequate support.

On the other hand, reading achievement is a key sign of how students are growing and progressing in school. It shows how well they understand, think about, and make sense of what they read. By following reading progress together with ARAL use, we can clearly see how the program helps improve reading skills. Melika et al. (2023) noted that reading is a crucial skill for our children today because it helps them develop a variety of talents and provides access to important information for jobs and education. Reading also helps pupils learn more and improve their overall learning.

Even though the ARAL Program has already been implemented nationwide, there are not enough studies on how it works in practice, especially in the Getafe 1 and 2 Districts. Most existing studies focus only on general recovery learning programs, without explicitly examining specific learning outcomes, such as reading proficiency. This establishes the deficiency this current study seeks to address, namely, whether schools that demonstrate readiness and responsiveness in ARAL Program implementation achieve greater reading outcomes for learners by correlating the extent of ARAL implementation with reading achievement.

This research provides educators, school leaders, and policymakers with useful insights into how the ARAL Program affects students' reading achievement. These insights can help schools improve the program's quality and results. Aside from determining its positive impacts, it can also help the Department of Education to identify which components of the ARAL Program need further support. In addition, the results of this study may contribute to ongoing efforts to strengthen literacy instruction in the country and ensure that every Filipino learner is a competent reader.

Thus, this study aims to give evidence-based recommendations for effective school-based planning, teacher training, and policy development. This study will not only evaluate the strengths and weaknesses of the ARAL Program's implementation but also emphasize the need to support learners in reading recovery and long-term academic achievement.

Theoretical Background

This study is anchored on several established educational theories. These theories offer a framework to comprehend the impact of recovery learning programs, such as the ARAL Program, and its impact on learners' reading skills through readiness assessment and evaluation. Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, Piaget's Cognitive

Development Theory, Bloom's Mastery Learning Theory, Bandura's Social Learning Theory, and Gunning's Proposition Theory are some of the most important theories that back up this study.

Lev Vygotsky (1978), in his Sociocultural Theory, sees learning and development as interconnected processes that aid in language acquisition. Vygotsky believed that children worked better together than alone. Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) framework explains the prospective performance. ZPD happens in interactive activities in which novices and experts work together to attain a goal.

In addition, Vygotskian scaffolding denotes direction or supervision. The support could come from an instructor or a student who is a little more or equal to the target learner. Such helpers act as a bridge between learners and the content they are attempting to comprehend, assisting them in achieving objectives that they could not attain on their own. ZPD emphasizes human interconnectedness and the role of social processes in the formation of all knowledge, including language.

Moreover, Jean Piaget (1952) posited that humans adapt to their physical and social environments. In his Cognitive Development Theory, he emphasized that adaptation commences at birth. Piaget conceptualized this adaptation through two fundamental processes: assimilation and accommodation. Assimilation is the process through which new objects and events are understood or integrated into pre-existing schemes or structures. This indicates that when encountering new information, individuals interpret it by referencing previously acquired knowledge and attempt to integrate the new information with existing cognitive frameworks. Accommodation refers to the modification of existing cognitive structures to address challenges in the straightforward understanding or assimilation of new objects or events.

Figure 1 Theoretical Framework

Moreover, to comprehend new information, one modifies existing knowledge structures to accommodate the new data. Piaget identifies four fundamental elements in development. (1) maturation, (2) experience, (3) social transmission involves the acquisition of knowledge through language, formal education, or parental instruction, and (4) Equilibrium. Piaget’s theory of cognitive development emphasizes a fixed progression through distinct stages. Piaget conceptualized cognitive development as a gradual transformation, recognizing that the growth is heterogeneous among individuals. Piaget posited that development occurs in a predetermined sequence.

Benjamin Bloom (1968) defines mastery learning as an instructional approach that assumes all individuals can learn when given suitable learning conditions. Mastery learning is a pedagogical approach in which

students progress to the next learning objective only after demonstrating proficiency in the current one. Benjamin Bloom's Mastery Learning was developed based on John B. Carroll's model of school learning from 1963. Bloom (1968) posited that if students exhibit a normal distribution in aptitude for a subject and receive uniform instruction regarding quality and learning duration, then their achievement upon completion of the subject would also follow a normal distribution. Bloom's concept posits that if each learner is provided with optimal instructional quality and sufficient learning time, the majority of students will achieve mastery.

Another theory that supports this study is the Social Learning Theory of Albert Bandura (1977), which emphasizes the importance of observing, modeling, and mimicking others' behaviors, attitudes, and emotional reactions. Individuals can learn new

behaviors not only via direct experience, but also by seeing others and witnessing the repercussions of their actions. Bandura argues that people are active information processors who consider the relationship between their actions and the consequences. The approach has been widely utilized in educational contexts, where teachers use modeling to display abilities and behaviors that they want students to imitate. One of its important features is observational learning, in which people learn and adopt behaviors by observing others. This process frequently entails modeling after people who are similar, high-status, knowledgeable, praised, or nurturing in our lives.

Bandura's Social Learning Theory supports the idea that learners can improve their reading proficiency skills through modelling and observation. In the context of education, teachers who serve as role models demonstrate to the learners how to read well, such as proper pronunciation, expression, and comprehension techniques. The learners then copy these actions until they become better at reading and speaking. Bandura's theory is one of the bases for the design of the ARAL Program, which focuses on modeling, feedback, and social interaction as these are important ways to improve learners' reading skills.

According to Gunning (1996) in his Proposition Theory, when the reader works through the text, they construct a primary notion or macrostructure. These main ideas are organized hierarchically, with the most important points given top priority for remembering. In other words, readers create information structures when reading a text. As they read, they convert the material into concepts or details that can be joined, removed, or incorporated to produce a cohesive macrostructure. Readers who can identify the primary idea are more likely to comprehend the content in depth.

Legal Bases

This study is anchored on the following legal bases to determine the relevance of this output to international and national goals. This includes laws and department directives, such as memoranda related to the present study.

The universal, holistic and indivisible 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development includes the special obligation to leave no one behind. It comprises 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which are inseparable and encompass economic, social, and environmental dimensions. One of its SDGs is SDG 4, which guarantees inclusive and equitable quality education and advocates lifelong learning opportunities for all. The strategies, principles, and actions for this goal serve as the contemporary

literacy knowledge as a continuum of proficiency levels in each setting or context. It goes beyond the simple understanding between literate and illiterate.

One of its targets by 2030 is to ensure that all young people and adults worldwide will have attained functional literacy and numeracy proficiency levels comparable to those achieved after basic education. The realization and achievement of SDG 4 play a crucial role in building sustainable, inclusive, and resilient societies. Under the Millennium Development Goals, there was a significant improvement in universal primary school enrolment. This new SDG 4 aims to set a higher standard and make education a driving force behind broader shifts toward sustainable development.

Republic Act No. 12028, also known as the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program Act, declares that the State shall endeavor to support learners by establishing a free and effective national learning intervention program to ensure that all learners who are struggling in their lessons, especially in reading, mathematics, and science, will be able to attain the competencies set by the Department of Education (DepEd) in their respective levels. This Act shall apply to the following learners from Kindergarten to Grade 10 under the public basic education institutions of the DepEd: (a) Those who have returned or are returning to school after a furlough; (b) Those who are below the minimum proficiency levels required in reading, mathematics, and science; or (c) Those who are failing in examinations and test as assessed and evaluated by the teachers during the course of the school year.

Republic Act No. 10533, also known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 Section (2), declares that the State shall establish, maintain, and support a complete, adequate, and integrated education system relevant to the needs of the people, the country, and society-at-large. Moreover, its central provision is that every person who completes basic education is required by this law to be an empowered individual who has mastered the fundamentals of lifelong learning. The law also stipulates that the State shall give a functional basic education system to produce responsible and competent individuals.

THE PROBLEM

Statement of the Problem

This study determined the relationship of implementing the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program on the reading skills and achievement of Key Stage 3 learners in Getafe 1 and 2 Districts, School Division of Bohol, for the school year 2025-2026 as a basis for an enhancement

program. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondent in terms of:
 - 1.1. Teachers'
 - 1.1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.1.2. civil status;
 - 1.1.3. performance rating;
 - 1.1.4. area of specialization;
 - 1.1.5. length of service;
 - 1.1.6. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.2. ARAL Learners'
 - 1.2.1. gender; and
 - 1.2.2. age?
2. As perceived by the teacher-respondents group, to what degree is the ARAL-Reading Program implemented based on ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASRRA) in terms of readiness across the following domains:
 - 2.1. learner;
 - 2.2. teacher/Tutor;
 - 2.3. school environment;
 - 2.4. parental;
 - 2.5. system support and governance?
3. What is the level of reading achievement of the Key Stage 3 learners after the ARAL implementation as to:
 - 3.1. frustration- struggling to read and has no comprehension;
 - 3.2. instructional- needs a little assistance in reading and shows little comprehension;
 - 3.3. independent- can read fluently and can understand the text on their own?
4. Is there a significant correlation between the implementation of the ARAL Program and the reading achievement of Key Stage 3 learners?
5. What enhancement program can be developed to strengthen the implementation of the ARAL Program and learners' reading achievement?

Statement of Hypothesis

H₀: There is no significant correlation between the implementation of the ARAL Program and learners' reading achievement.

Significance of the Study

The results of this study have the potential to offer significant empirical evidence and insights that can guide policy formulation and enhance decision-making processes about the subject matter. The researcher believed that this study would be beneficial to the following:

Education Policymakers. The findings of the study may help them craft and strengthen policies and

programs to support the effective implementation of the ARAL Program and enhance the learners' reading achievement. The results would also give them the idea to provide resources for teacher training, instructional materials, support systems in schools, and community involvement to have an equitable and quality literacy development.

School Administrators. The outcome of the study guides the administrators to provide information about the effectiveness of the ARAL program implementation and how it helps to improve learners' reading proficiency and achievement. Through the results, they will be able to identify the areas that need to be improved and devise activities and strategies to further support the implementation of the ARAL program.

Teachers. The findings of this study give the teachers more insights into how the ARAL program helps the learners improve their reading abilities. This also provides them with opportunities to improve their teaching strategies based on approaches that promote fluency and comprehension. Moreover, this gives them more ideas to offer differentiated instruction that tailors to learners' reading needs and abilities.

Students. The study's findings help them in their quest to succeed academically and would significantly aid them in developing their reading knowledge, skills, and talents. This study motivates them to think about how important it is to read actively. The improved implementation of the ARAL program provides them with more opportunities to strengthen their abilities and develop self-confidence in reading.

Future Researchers. The study can be a reference material to researchers who want to explore related topics in reading intervention strategies and learning recovery programs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This section describes the systematic process utilized to carry out the study, beginning with the research design that frames the investigation. It describes the study's flow using the Input-Process-Output model, including how data are acquired, processed, and utilized. The study's environment and respondents are identified first, followed by the data collection instruments, which include validated questionnaires and academic records. The data collection technique is discussed in three stages: preparatory, data gathering, and post-data gathering, to ensure ethical and correct information handling. Statistical methods for data analysis are also offered, as are the scoring systems for interpreting the extent of ARAL program implementation and learners' reading achievement.

Design

This study employed a quantitative-correlational research design to determine the relationship between the ARAL program implementation and the reading achievement of Junior High School learners in the Getafe 2 District. The correlational research design is appropriate because this study aims to determine the association between two variables without manipulating either of them.

In this study, the variable under investigation is the ARAL program implementation and learners’ reading achievement. The ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASRRA) was used to measure the extent of ARAL program implementation. On the other hand, reading achievement was evaluated

through the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) or ARAL reading proficiency data per school. Moreover, the collected data was analyzed and interpreted through inferential statistics to determine whether a connection exists between two variables or not.

In addition, the study utilized a purposive sampling to ensure that the intended respondents will be included, since each school has already identified ARAL learners and tutors. The selection emphasized those individuals who already have a direct or firsthand experience in the implementation of the program.

Flow of the Study This study observed the Input-Process-Output (IPO) model in handling the data. Figure 2 illustrates the model.

Figure 2 Research Flow

The input stage of this study contains the essential elements based on the statement of the problem. These include the respondents’ profiles such as sex, and grade level, civil status, performance rating, area of specialization, length of service, and highest educational attainment; the extent of ARAL program implementation; learners’ reading achievement; and the significant relationship between these two variables. Additionally, these inputs serve as the basis for guiding the objectives formation and the development of research instruments to be utilized in data collection.

The process stage involves the steps to be undertaken in analyzing and collecting the data. The researcher first distributed the transmittal letters to ask permission to conduct the study. The study used descriptive correlational data, where it seeks to find a connection between the ARAL program implementation and learners’ reading achievement. Data was collected using standardized questionnaires and was analyzed through various descriptive and correlational tools. The results were examined and interpreted to create useful conclusions and recommendations.

The study's output is a proposed enhancement plan to strengthen the implementation of the ARAL program and the reading achievement of Junior High School learners in Getafe 2 District. Its goal is to make the ARAL program better and more effective by filling in the gaps that have been found in readiness, instructional practices, and learner support systems.

Environment

Getafe is a 92-kilometer-long port town on the northern coast of Bohol Province. The town of Getafe had a projected population of 33 579 in 2012 and has a land area of 99.80 sq. km. It has 24 barangays- seven (7) island barangays, and the remaining lie along the mainland coast. The island barangays are Alumar, Banacon, Jagolio, Jandayan Norte, Mahanay, Nasingin and Pandanon. The mainland barangays are Buyog, Cabasakan, Campao Occidental, Campao Oriental, Cangmundo, Carlos P. Garcia, Corte Baud, Handumon, Jandayan Sur, Poblacion, Saguis, Salog, San Jose, Santo Niño, Taytay, Tugas, and Tulang.

Handumon National High School aspires to cultivate empowered, responsible, and value-oriented learners equipped to make significant contributions to society. The school was founded in June 1998 with the assistance of the Barangay Local Government Unit and the parents of Barangay Handumon, Getafe, Bohol. Handumon National High School was formed to provide outstanding education. It is located in Barangay Handumon, Getafe, Bohol, approximately four (4) kilometers from the town center and ninety-one (91) kilometers from Tagbilaran, the capital of Bohol. It has thirty-seven (37) teachers and three (3) non-teaching personnel, headed by Mrs. Gladys Mae O. Pogoy.

This study was also conducted at Tulang National High School in Tulang, Getafe, Bohol. It is approximately 95 kilometers away from Tagbilaran City. The school has forty-three (43) teaching and five (5) non-teaching personnel headed by Dr. Rex S. Cuizon. The school offers Junior High School and Senior High School education.

Campao Oriental High School is situated in Campao Oriental, Getafe, Bohol. It is approximately 85 kilometers away from Tagbilaran and 10 kilometers way from the town center. The school has thirty-seven (37) teaching personnel and five (5) non-teaching personnel, headed by Ruel G. Agodo. The school offers Junior High School and Senior High School education.

Pandanon High School is an island school located in Pandanon, Getafe, Bohol. It is also located in the Danajon Bank, the only double-barrier reef in the country, and is famous for its rich marine wildlife. It is approximately 9 kilometers northwest of the port of Getafe. It has thirteen (13) teachers and two (2) non-teaching staff, headed by Mr. Pepe J. Torreon Jr. The school also offers Junior High School and Senior High School education.

Figure 3 Location Map of the Study

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the ARAL teachers and the identified ARAL learners enrolled in Junior High School level of the four (4) public secondary schools in Getafe 1 and 2 Districts for the school year 2025-2026, namely: Handumon National High School, Tulang National High School, Campao Oriental High School, Pandanon High School. They were chosen as the respondents of the study because they are the direct recipients of the ARAL program. The distribution of respondents is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Distribution of the Respondents

Name of School	Teachers	Learners	Total	%
Handumon National High School	4	90	94	35.34
Tulang National High School	4	45	49	18.42
Campao Oriental High School	12	67	79	29.70
Pandanon High School	4	40	44	16.54
TOTAL	24	242	266	100

The table above shows the distribution of the respondents with 266 respondents being included in the study which is composed of 24 teachers and 244 learners among the four secondary schools. Handumon National High School had the highest number of respondents with 94 or 35.34%, followed by Campao Oriental High School with 79 or 29.70%, Tulang National High School with 49 or 18.42%, and Pandanon High School with 44 or 16.44%.

Instruments

The researcher used a survey questionnaire to collect the information needed to achieve the study's goals. To obtain data on the extent of the ARAL program implementation and assess the preparation of schools, the researcher will utilize and adopt the ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASRRA) of the Department of Education. This tool contains 5 domains, which include Learner Readiness, Teacher/Tutor Readiness, School Environment Readiness, Parental Readiness, and System Support Readiness.

Meanwhile, the researcher utilized the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) or ARAL reading proficiency data to obtain the data on the reading achievement of the learners.

Data Gathering Procedure

Preliminary Stage. The researcher asked first for endorsement from the research teacher and the Dean of the Graduate School. Then, the researcher secured approval to conduct the study from the Division of Bohol Superintendent, District Supervisors, and School Heads of the four (4) public secondary schools in Getafe 1 and 2 Districts for the school year 2025-2026. In this stage, the researcher further informed and guaranteed that the anonymity of the respondents involved was strictly adhered to. In addition, the researcher explained the study's purpose, scope, and ethical considerations to ensure that it adhered to the research protocols of the Department of Education.

Data Gathering Stage. After obtaining permission to conduct the study, the researcher coordinated with the ARAL Coordinators and ARAL teachers to ask their permission to answer the ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASSRA) questionnaire. The data from the ASSRA were used to determine the degree of ARAL program implementation in terms of Learner Readiness, Teacher/Tutor Readiness, School Environment Readiness, Parental Readiness, and System Support Readiness. For the learners' reading achievement records, the researcher collected the school data for the PHIL-IRI of the ARAL learners.

Post Data Gathering Stage. After the collection of data, the researcher tallied and organized the data in tables for tabulation and analysis. The ASSRA results were interpreted to determine the degree of ARAL program implementation, while the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) or ARAL reading achievement of the learners was categorized into Independent, Instructional, and Frustration to determine learners' reading level. Afterwards, the results and findings of the study were interpreted to infer conclusions and recommendations that were the basis of the Proposed Enhancement Program to strengthen ARAL program implementation and further improve learners' reading skills among the Junior High School learners in Getafe 2 District.

Statistical Treatment

After all the data had been gathered, it was subjected to statistical analysis and interpretation. The data from the survey and reading achievement records were sorted, summarized, and evaluated using statistical tools. The collected data from the ASSRA and learners' reading proficiency level were analyzed and interpreted to

determine the degree of relationship between the extent of ARAL program implementation and learners' reading achievement.

Frequency Count and Percentage. This was used to determine the total number of respondents who belong in the same category of their profile, such as sex and grade level, and the distribution of the learners' reading proficiency levels.

Weighted Mean. This tool was used to determine the average level as to the extent of ARAL program implementation as assessed by the five domains of ASSRA: learner readiness, teacher/tutor readiness, school environment readiness, parental readiness, and system support and governance readiness.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). This tool was employed to test the degree of significant relationship between the extent of ARAL program implementation readiness and the Key Stage 3 learners' (Junior High School learners) reading achievement.

The data was tabulated and analyzed using statistical software to ensure that the results are valid and reliable.

Scoring Procedure

To analyze and understand the data, the researcher created a scoring system to quantify the responses of the ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASSRA) and the learners' reading achievement.

The ASSRA instrument evaluated the extent of ARAL program implementation, which contains 5 key domains: Learner Readiness, Teacher/Tutor Readiness, School Environment Readiness, Parental Readiness, and System Support Readiness. There are three options to assess these five (5) domains: Met, Partially Met, and Not Met. These options are given with corresponding numerical values for quantitative analysis, as shown below.

Response Option	Numerical Value	Scale	Interpretation
Met	3	2.34-3.0	Fully Implemented
Partially Met	2	1.67-2.33	Partially Implemented
Not Met	1	1.0-1.66	Not Implemented

The overall level of implementation of the ARAL Program was based on the mean scores from each domain. Higher mean scores demonstrate that the program is more ready and responsive, while lower mean scores show that there are areas that need more work.

Furthermore, the scoring procedure for the learners' reading achievement was based on the PHIL-IRI results or any ARAL reading assessment conducted by the school. Each learner was categorized into three reading proficiency levels, namely: Frustration, Instructional, and Independent. These reading proficiency levels are given corresponding numerical values for quantitative analysis, as shown below.

Reading Proficiency Levels	Numerical Value	Scale	Description
Independent	3	2.34-3.0	The learner can read fluently and can understand the text on their own.
Instructional	2	1.67-2.33	The learner needs a little assistance or helps from the teacher and shows little comprehension.
Frustration	1	1.0-1.66	The learner is struggling to read and has trouble understanding the text.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

The following words are defined as used in this study to minimize ambiguity and ensure a clear understanding of the technical terms. These definitions are based on how it is used in the context of the study entitled "ARAL Program Implementation: Its Correlation to JHS Reading Achievement in Getafe 2 District."

Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program. A learning recovery program of the Department of Education designed to support learners who demonstrate below-minimum proficiency levels in foundational learning domains, particularly reading and mathematics, and to accelerate their mastery of grade-level competencies through structured, high-impact interventions.

ARAL Coordinator. It refers to the teacher or school official who is designated to coordinate and lead the implementation of the ARAL program in the school.

ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASRRA). It is a structured, school-based audit tool used to assess the capacity and preparedness of schools to implement the ARAL Program across five domains.

Correlation. A statistical measure used to determine the degree of relationship between two variables, in this study, the ARAL program implementation and learners' reading achievement.

Correlational Research Design. A statistical tool used to identify the degree of relationship between two variables.

Data Gathering Procedure. It refers to the systematic process of collecting data undertaken by the researcher in the study.

Department of Education (DepEd). A Philippine government agency responsible for managing and governing the basic education system in the country.

DepEd Memorandum. It refers to the official policy document by the Department of Education used to share and convey information about the implementation of national programs and activities such as ARAL.

Domains of Readiness. The five critical areas of school functionality assessed under the ASRRA: (1) Learner Readiness, (2) Teacher /Tutor Readiness, (3) School Environment Readiness, (4) Parental Engagement Readiness, and (5) System Support & Governance Readiness. These domains collectively determine the school's preparedness to implement ARAL.

Enhancement Program. It refers to the proposed plan based on the findings of the study to further strengthen the ARAL implementation and learners' reading achievement.

Getafe 2 District. The group of public secondary schools in the Municipality of Getafe, under the Department of Education, Division of Bohol.

Implementation. The steps that need to be taken to put the ARAL Program into action in the school, such as planning, carrying out, and keeping an eye on learning interventions.

Instructional Support. It refers to the teachers' support in helping students meet the learning objectives in reading and other subjects.

Intervention. It is a set of actions that a teacher or administrator takes to address any gaps in a learner's progress or attainment.

Junior High School (JHS). It refers to the educational level from Grade 7- Grade 10 under the K-12 Basic Education Program.

Learner Readiness. This domain concentrates on finding, tagging, and evaluating the preparedness of learners qualified for the ARAL Program.

Learning Loss. It refers to the reduction in knowledge and skills that learners may face, typically due to prolonged breaks or interruptions in their education.

Learning Outcomes. This refers to the statements that describe the learners' knowledge, skills, and competencies they need to achieve at the end of a particular program.

Learning Recovery. This is the process of recovering or regaining learning losses through implementing various programs such as ARAL.

Parental Engagement Readiness. This domain evaluates the participation and assistance of parents/guardians and the Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) in executing the ARAL Program. It encompasses informed permission, parental orientations, and voluntary donations that adhere to DepEd standards for child protection and non-collection.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). It is a statistical tool that measures the strength of the association or connection between two variables.

Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). It is an informal reading assessment used by the teachers to determine the learners' reading proficiency level, such as Independent, Instruction, and Frustration.

Program Implementation Level. This refers to the extent to which a program's goals and activities are met in accordance with established standards.

Reading Achievement. It is the learners' reading performance level evaluated through a standardized reading assessment such as PHIL-IRI.

Reading Comprehension. It is the ability of the learners to understand something that has been read. It is an intellectual ability to grasp the meaning of the desired text.

Reading Proficiency Levels. It refers to the learner's reading proficiency category, such as Frustration, Instructional, and Independent.

Respondents. These refer to the identified ARAL learners from Handumon National High School and Tulang National High School who participated in the study.

School Environment Readiness. This area evaluates the physical, instructional, and protective conditions of the school that facilitate the secure and efficient implementation of ARAL sessions. It encompasses specialized learning environments, resources, apparatus, and accessibility provisions, particularly in educational institutions located in underprivileged or high-need regions.

Stakeholders. These are the individuals who are involved in the ARAL program, such as teachers, learners, parents, and administrators.

System Support and Governance Readiness. This domain assesses the incorporation of the ARAL Program into educational planning, budgeting, and governance frameworks, encompassing the involvement of support personnel, the effective utilization of Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE), Special Education Fund (SEF), and additional resources, as well as the formation of external partnerships and reporting systems.

Teacher/Tutor Readiness. This area examines the availability, qualifications, and deployment of ARAL Program implementers, including teachers, para-teachers, and other qualified tutors. It evaluates their training, subject alignment, compliance with ratios, and institutional support systems.

2. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This study is anchored on the following related literature to provide an overview of the current knowledge and provide the foundation of knowledge on the topic. Through looking at the past and present studies, the researcher can comprehend and understand more about the context of the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning Program and its influence on learners' reading achievement.

Related Literature

Reading enables children to absorb material independently, while teachers establish clear, sequential instructional methods. It disrupts the students' lack of interest by motivating them to engage more actively and effectively in the educational process. Therefore, employing tactics that improve learners' reading comprehension is essential. Furthermore, reading comprehension is considered the fundamental element of the reading process and the primary process around which all other processes revolve. It constitutes the foundation of all reading processes and the pinnacle of reading proficiency (Fernando & Ambayon, 2024).

As stressed by Campilla & Cariño (2024), reading is crucial for comprehending written content during teaching and learning. The students' comprehension of the text's content is equally vital as their comprehension of the written symbol. Reading comprehension is the process of determining what something means by combining several complex procedures, such as reading words, interpreting words, and speaking fluently.

Soria (2024) argued that the rapid rise in education underscores the need to learn English, encompassing reading, speaking, writing, and listening. Reading is an essential life skill that everyone should have, enabling people to read and interpret written language and granting them access to knowledge, diverse perspectives, critical thinking, and global wisdom. Moreover, comprehension is a critical component of reading ability and a complex process in which readers actively engage with the text, incorporating prior knowledge, experiences, and unique viewpoints.

The ability to read is essential for understanding the world around us as well as ourselves. Life can be difficult if you do not read well. The future of today's learners is dependent on their ability to comprehend and apply a diverse range of texts thoughtfully. It also depends on their ability to employ reading abilities to think critically and express themselves orally and in writing. Recognizing the value of reading, many industrialized countries have established reading programs to encourage reading and help young kids improve their reading. These programs have different designs and information. Some concentrate on improving the quality of reading

instruction provided by teachers and parents, while others try to increase the quantity of available reading materials (Adapon & Mangila, 2020).

In the Philippines, education is impeded by poverty, technological deficiencies, and a lack of motivation and inspiration, particularly in reading instruction. There are many Filipinos who are not able to acquire knowledge, regardless of their socio-economic level. There are certain households that lack enough financial resources to enroll their children in school; consequently, these children mature without literacy skills. Some families are somewhat fortunate to send their children to a public school; however, the children are acquiring poor and slow fundamental reading skills because of insufficient teachers and outdated reading materials at the institution. A remedial reading program has long been maintained within the Philippine basic school system. Genero's study (as cited in Adapon & Mangila, 2020) revealed how the nation's primary and secondary schools used remedial reading programs to assist struggling readers. With this, principals should motivate their educators to assess their students' reading levels to facilitate suitable interventions (Adapon & Mangila, 2020).

Moreover, Nailon et al. (2023) stated that learners facing reading difficulties may need support to enhance their competency in decoding the text. Some individuals may initially excel due to their adept recognition of sight words, yet may have difficulties as reading demands become more complex in grade 2 and thereafter. For instance, for a learner in grade 7 or higher who exhibits reading difficulties, it is important to provide them additional guidance to enhance their foundational phonics understanding, which should have been established in kindergarten and grade 1. This can be accomplished by using educational resources such as flashcards or phonics worksheets to strengthen comprehension of sound-letter associations. A strong foundation in phonics can greatly improve a student's reading skills. Consequently, by concentrating on the fundamental abilities inherent in reading, students are equipped with additional resources to enhance their overall reading proficiency.

Learning institutions, administrators, and teachers play a major role in effectively implementing reading programs. The contextualization of reading programs within educational institutions constitutes a commendable practice. Nevertheless, the methods used by certain school administrators in selecting reading coordinators reflect a lack of equity. While educators participate in training sessions, school administrators need to incorporate those accountable for the reading program. Furthermore, to properly administer a program or intervention, school managers should approach decision-making proactively, and educators should be enthusiastic about teaching.

As a result, cohesiveness and comprehension are critical to meeting the project's objectives. The task for guiding pupils to become proficient readers should not be primarily placed on teachers. Their parents may also play a very important role in implementing reading programs, as reading not only includes students' reading abilities but also their behavioral and emotional dimensions, which are best understood by parents. Consequently, a collaborative partnership between home and school warrants consideration (Lucero, 2019).

In this regard, home assistance also helps learners develop good reading habits. As a post-pandemic remedial intervention, catch-up reading sessions help young learners regain foundational reading skills lost during remote schooling. Learners should get catch-up reading sessions as part of the reading curriculum to improve phonemic awareness, vocabulary, and comprehension. Parents can easily monitor their children's progress through remedial measures at home. Additionally, children are considerably more likely to engage in literacy activities when their parents are consistently involved. This helps them go back to basic reading abilities that were lost during distance learning during the pandemic.

Furthermore, providing meaningful, culturally appropriate reading materials and activities tailored to the developmental stages of junior high school teenage learners helps them achieve reading competency. Moreover, educators must receive professional training in ICT-enabled reading pedagogy to improve interaction and comprehension. When combined with interactive ICT tools, such as multimedia resources and online collaboration platforms, the content can offer a multimodal learning experience that accommodates various learning styles (Casinto, 2025).

However, reading difficulties are a major issue worldwide, not just in the Philippines. According to the 2022 Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), the Philippines ranked lowest in reading comprehension. Data from the Functional Literacy, Education, and Mass Media Survey also shows that about 20.1 million Filipinos struggle with reading comprehension.

To help solve these problems, the Department of Education has started several programs to improve reading instruction and resources. One example is the National Learning Camp (NLC), part of the National Learning

Recovery Program, which aims to help students recover from learning losses caused by the pandemic. The NLC offers personalized camps that focus on improving reading skills, especially for students in grades 7 to 10. The NLC, which includes Enhancement, Consolidation, and Intervention camps, aims to reduce pandemic-related learning deficits, notably in reading comprehension (Soria, 2024).

For the 2025-2026 school year, the Department of Education expanded its recovery efforts through the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program. It institutionalizes tutorial sessions and continuous reading assessments to ensure long-term improvement in learners' reading achievement.

The ARAL Program is hereby instituted to serve as a nationwide learning intervention initiative for students from Kindergarten to Grade 10 enrolled in public basic education, including learners participating in the Alternative Learning System. This initiative supports learners by implementing a free and effective national learning intervention program to make sure that all students with difficulties in their lessons, particularly in reading, mathematics, and science, can achieve the competencies established by the Department of Education (DepEd) at their respective levels. The ARAL Program will include the 24 core learning competencies specified in the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum. These competencies cover literacy and mathematics for Grades 1 to 10, as well as science for Grades 3 to 10. Within the ARAL Program, reading and mathematics will be prioritized to enhance learners' critical and analytical thinking and to develop 21st-century skills (Department of Education, 2024).

The Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning Program in Reading (ARAL-Reading) aims to help students who don't meet expected reading proficiency standards quickly, in a way that works for them and is effective. This will help them meet the Department of Education (DepEd) grade-level expectations. ARAL-Reading helps students in grades 1 to 10 improve their reading skills by offering structured, learner-focused lessons that match each student's reading level, not just their age or grade. In addition, for SY 2025—2026, ARAL-Reading shall prioritize Low and High Emerging learners in Key Stage 1 and learners in the Frustration level in Key Stages 2 and 3. However, schools with the needed personnel and other resources are encouraged to extend the program to Developing and Transitioning learners in Key Stage 1 and Instructional learners in Key Stages 2 and 3.

Furthermore, the following activities are conducted in preparation for ARAL-Reading: Beginning of School Year (BOSY) assessments, ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASRRA), profiling and grouping learners, recruiting, assigning, and training tutors, preparing teacher and class programs, orienting field implementers, tutors, parents, and learners, and vision and health-related screening (DepEd Memorandum 064, s. 2025).

Similarly, ARAL prioritized Reading (ARAL-Reading) to offer immediate support to students in need, particularly those who are low and high-emerging readers, as well as those experiencing frustration in reading. As of this year, the Department of Education has identified 6,713,352 students as beneficiaries of the program, supported by 447,537 tutors and 45,084 school heads. ARAL-Reading is scheduled to commence in the second quarter of the school year 2025–2026. The program will subsequently expand to encompass ARAL-Mathematics (Grades 1–10), ARAL-Science (Grades 3–10), and ARAL-Summer Programs. To ensure preparedness, the Department of Education has conducted training for tutors, distributed educational resources, and initiated the ARAL School Readiness and Responsiveness Audit (ASRRA) (Guzman, 2025).

In addition, the parents and guardians will be involved through orientations to enhance their role in supporting their children's learning at home and reinforcing program lessons. The ARAL Program builds on the achievements of previous literacy initiatives by the Department of Education, including the Bawat Bata Makababasa Program (BBMP) and the Nationwide Learning Recovery Program (NLRP), both of which demonstrated notable improvements in reading and learning outcomes among participating students.

Related Studies

According to Bitanes and Estera (2025), the Brigada Pagbasa program helps students enhance their motivation, comprehension, and reading fluency. The research revealed that students in rural, multigrade settings could improve their literacy through community involvement and volunteer labor. Parents became more engaged and cognizant of their children's educational requirements, and educators and volunteers collaborated more closely. Overall, Brigada Pagbasa was an effective support program for boosting literacy in multigrade classrooms.

The study suggests ongoing support, training, and monitoring to keep the program effective and responsive to students' needs. To keep Brigada Pagbasa going, schools should improve introduction sessions, test reading skills on a regular basis, assure adequate resources, and provide ongoing training to volunteers and teachers.

Increased involvement of parents and community members can lead to better outcomes, especially in multigrade settings. Program directors should seek technical assistance in developing activities that improve volunteer training, recruitment, and parental involvement.

In the study of Wiliam et al. (2025) entitled “The Effect of Reading Interventions and Programs on Literacy Rates in Philippine Elementary Schools”, revealed that Reading programs, especially those focusing on phonics and balanced literacy, show positive results. The impact on improving literacy rates. Non-governmental organization (NGOs) programs were especially effective in rural areas, where community involvement was vital in aiding struggling kids. Government measures were good, but had varied effects, especially in areas with little resources and teacher training.

The National Learning Camp (NLC) has helped boost students' academic performance and participation. With targeted support and new teaching methods, students have made gains in reading, math, and critical thinking. These results show that NLC adds value to regular school programs by providing students with extra help and more opportunities to learn, helping them grow as individuals. (Gagabe et al., 2024)

Some schools have managed to include the NLC in their programs, but others have run into difficulties. This shows the need for clear guidelines and best practices. Teachers working with the NLC should receive ongoing training in new teaching methods, personalized instruction, and the use of technology in class. Setting up a mentoring and coaching system can also help teachers as they use the NLC curriculum and meet different student needs. To make sure the program works well everywhere, schools need clear guidelines and ways to measure progress. These should cover how to add the NLC to the curriculum, how to assess students, and how to involve the community.

Furthermore, the National Learning Camps (NLC) have had a strong positive impact on student learning, especially in reading and numeracy skills for Grade 2 students (Berry, 2024). After the intervention, students showed clear improvements in both reading comprehension and numeracy. These results highlight how structured programs like NLC can help solve academic challenges and support overall student growth. It is important to keep building on and expanding NLC activities to ensure all students have equal access and lasting educational benefits. Policymakers and educators can use these findings to adapt teaching methods to better meet the needs of primary school learners.

Similarly, the study by Abad & Vargas (2024) found that the difficulties encountered by the English Teacher Volunteers during the execution of NLC affected several aspects of the program in complex ways. Recruiting and retaining learners in remote areas requires creative solutions, and financial limitations encourage them. The complexity of the modules and problems with time management underscore the need for customized learning resources and flexible timetables. Language challenges require sophisticated approaches, such as specialized programs and mother-tongue delivery. Optimizing the NLC program's implementation requires a thorough strategy that addresses linguistic, logistical, pedagogical, and economic factors.

The study of Salibay (2024), entitled “Enhancing Literacy: A Comparative Analysis of the Effectiveness of Project Bear and Arangkada Pagbasa Reading Interventions in Claver National High School”, assesses the efficacy of two reading intervention programs, PROJECT B.E.A.R. (Being Excited About Reading) and ARANGKADA PAGBASA, at Claver National High School during two academic years (2022-2024). The Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) pretest initially identified numerous students as deficient readers. Post-intervention findings revealed a significant enhancement in reading skills, underscoring the efficacy of both programs. The study emphasizes the significance of collaborative initiatives among educators, parents, and the local government unit (L.G.U.) in tackling reading issues.

Both Project B.E.A.R. and ARANGKADA PAGBASA helped improve students' reading skills, especially with support from parents and the local government. Based on these results, the researcher recommends using reading intervention activities to help students who struggle with reading. The study also suggests that solving reading problems requires cooperation among students, teachers, parents, and the local government.

Montallana and Velasco (2022) found a partial link between Grade 9 students' reading comprehension and the parts of Project REACH. The school should keep supporting and improving Project REACH, involve all students in the program, and follow its motto, "no child will be left behind." The study showed a significant improvement in Grade 9 students' English test scores after the program. Therefore, language teachers are encouraged to provide more reading materials that build both reading skills and comprehension.

Project REACH had a positive effect on the reading comprehension of the students. After the project began, students showed clear improvement in their reading skills. There was a strong connection between their reading levels before and after the REACH initiative (Graciano, 2024). Interventions that use phonics-based instruction and balanced literacy approaches help improve literacy rates. Programs run by non-governmental organizations worked especially well in rural areas, where community support was important for helping students who struggled. Government programs also made a difference, but their results were mixed, especially in areas with fewer resources and less teacher training (William et al., 2025).

The success of these interventions depended on teacher preparation, student involvement, and support from the community. Some programs faced challenges such as resource constraints, uneven implementation, and differences between urban and rural schools. Even with these issues, the overall results show that well-run reading programs can greatly improve literacy in elementary schools across the Philippines..

As mentioned by McBreen & Savage (2022) the remedial reading instruction exerts a more significant influence on different facets of reading performance and motivation when it is integrated with evidence-based and theory-informed strategies designed to enhance motivation. Results indicate that developing reading programs that integrate skills-based instruction with motivational support—by providing goal-oriented, progress-focused, and autonomy-enhancing teaching—can produce more favorable outcomes than programs that solely emphasize the cognitive dimensions of reading acquisition.

3. PRESENTATION, DATA ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

This chapter presents the data obtained from the respondents of the study with the corresponding analysis and interpretation. The respondents of this study consisted of 24 teachers and 242 ARAL learners for a total of 266 respondent groups from the secondary schools in the Getafe 1 and 2 Districts of Bohol Division.

This chapter comprised four (4) distinct sections.

The first part shows with the profile of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, civil status, performance rating, area of specialization, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

The second part of this chapter deals with the degree of ARAL Program implementation in terms of learner readiness; teacher readiness; school environment readiness; parental readiness; and system support and governance readiness.

The third part assesses the level of learners' reading skills after the ARAL program implementation

Lastly, this study tests the significant correlation between the learners' profiles and their reading achievement. In addition, the study also tests the relationship between the ARAL Program implementation readiness and the learners' reading achievement.

RELEVANT INFORMATION OF THE RESPONDENTS

The following tables reveal the relevant information of the respondents in terms of their age, gender, civil status, performance rating, area of specialization, length of service, and highest educational attainment.

Age. Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of age.

Table 2 Age Profile

Age	Frequency (n=24)	Percentage (100%)
51 years old and above	4	16.66
41-50 years old	6	25
31-40 years old	7	29.17
21-30 years old	7	29.17
Total	24	100
Average	38.33	-
Standard Deviation	10.46	-

Table 2 illustrates the age distribution of the 24 teacher-respondents who participated in the study. The findings indicate that 29.17% of respondents fall within the age group of 31 to 40 years and 21 to 30 years. Subsequently, 6 respondents or 25% are inside the 41 to 50 age brackets, and merely 16.66% fall between the ages of 51 years old and above. The computed mean age of 38.33 years, accompanied by a standard deviation of 10.46, suggests that a significant proportion of the respondents are situated within their thirties, thereby implying a teaching staff characterized by relative experience and maturity. This age distribution reflects a beneficial combination of

professional competence among educators who have established enduring careers within the educational sector. Pablo et al. (2025) posit that public-school teachers typically reflect upon their professional experiences during their middle years. A survey conducted across several Philippine schools revealed that teachers aged between 36 and 40 exhibited a strong commitment to their roles, remaining in academia due to a sense of vocation.

Furthermore, Reyna and Ardiente's (2025) findings support this observation, showing that many teachers are in their thirties. This age group is often associated with a good balance of energy, professional skill, and independence, suggesting they are well-equipped to handle the challenges of modern teaching. In contrast, those over fifty-one are usually considered experienced educators.

Teachers over 51 years old are generally considered veteran or experienced educators. Their long service to the school system greatly contributes to its ongoing effectiveness and stability. As mentioned by the report of OECD (2023), experienced teachers usually possess a high level of pedagogical knowledge, strong classroom management skills, and have professional values that allow them to support the creation and maintenance of effective learning environments for their students.

Additionally, Darling-Hammond et al. (2022) stated that teachers with extensive teaching experience tend to have greater levels of professional commitment and instructional expertise than other teachers; therefore, their teaching experience will positively impact student learning and school improvement efforts.

Overall, the age distribution indicates that the corresponding teaching workforce of the Department of Education would include various mid-career professionals with sufficient experience and motivation to perform well. As stated by UNESCO (2023), a diverse teaching workforce that includes older teachers, recent graduates, and younger teachers fosters mentoring, knowledge transfer, and professional learning, creating the conditions for improvement of educational outcomes and stronger education systems.

Gender. Table 3 presents the profile of the respondents in terms of gender.

Table 3 Gender Profile

Gender	Frequency (n=24)	Percentage (100%)
Female	19	79.17
Male	5	20.83
Total	24	100

Table 3 demonstrates the profile of the respondents in terms of their gender. It shows a clear predominance of female teachers, comprising 19 or 79.17% of the population, while male teachers comprise only 5 or 20.83%. The results indicate that almost all teachers in the study area are women. This is typical of the Philippine education system, where teaching is seen as a job mostly for women.

This aligns with the data from the World Bank's development indicators, which show that in 2024, the proportion of female teachers in primary education in the Philippines was 88.3%. The female majority in the teaching profession may not have changed much, if at all; women remain positioned in basic education roles as reflective of the deeply entrenched socio-cultural tropes and economic structures reinforcing gendered careers in education (World Bank, 2025). In addition, although male respondents in basic education comprise a smaller proportion of the relevant population, in this study, they accounted for 20.83% of the total respondents. In 2024, 100 percent of male teachers in both primary and secondary education in the Philippines were classified as trained teachers (World Bank, 2025). It only means that although male teachers are fewer, those who were hired in the teaching profession are equally qualified as the female teachers.

Nonetheless, while the teaching profession is seen to be female-dominated in primary and secondary education, both male and female teachers bring unique pedagogical strategies and techniques that would benefit the students and the school in general. As mentioned by Olvido et al. (2024), female educators are more likely to be supportive, patient, and motivate students to engage and participate in group activities and ask guiding questions. They offer "warm responses" that foster peer collaboration, underscore the importance of higher-order thinking skills, and share their experiences as diverse learners. On the other hand, males are the ones who initiate teacher-student interactions by asking precise questions, exercising greater authority, and employing a task-centered teaching style. The number of male teachers is decreasing; however, they contribute unique perspectives on discipline and class administration.

Civil Status. Table 4 reveals the profile of the respondents in terms of their civil status.

Table 4 Civil Status Profile

Civil Status	Frequency (n=24)	Percentage (100%)
Married	18	75
Single	6	25
Total	24	100

Table 4 shows the civil status profile of the teacher-respondents. The table reveals that majority of the respondents, comprising 18 or 75% are married, while the other 6 or 25% are identified as single. The data suggests that a significant percentage of teachers come from stable familial backgrounds, a factor often linked to heightened levels of responsibility, maturity, and commitment to their pedagogical roles. Teachers who are married tend to demonstrate a strong sense of work-life balance, with their responsibilities in their family which shaped their instructional methodologies and student interactions.

Pablo et al. (2025) further observed that married teachers displayed notable distinctions in their approach to professional obligations, punctuality, collaborative efforts, self-efficacy, emotional regulation, and sense of responsibility, in contrast to their unmarried peers. Consequently, an individual's marital status can exert a considerable influence on their performance values and work ethic. Married teachers often have unique perspectives on their work, which affects how they collaborate, how they manage their time, and other important professional skills. Overall, the data on marital status shows that most teachers are married, with a smaller group of single educators.

The civil status profile generally shows that the teaching workforce is mostly made up of married individuals, with a smaller group of single educators. However, Bibas and Isarail (2022) found no significant differences in work-life quality for teachers based on their marital status. The researchers found that a teacher's relationship status didn't necessarily affect their work experiences or how satisfied they were with their jobs. In other words, both single and married teachers made important contributions to school results and classroom performance.

Performance Rating. Table 5 shows the performance rating of the respondents.

Table 5 Performance Rating

Performance Rating	Frequency (n=24)	Percentage (100%)
Outstanding	1	4.17
Very Satisfactory	23	95.83
Total	24	100

As shown in Table 5, the majority of the teacher respondents' ratings were "Very Satisfactory". Of the 24 teachers, 23 (95.83%) received this rating, while only 1 (4.17%) received "Outstanding." This indicates that most of the respondents possessed the quality of an effective teacher, suggesting a commitment to personal growth and professional development.

According to Chen and Mohammed (2024), the primary objective of education is to cultivate an environment conducive to superior instruction and learning across all educational strata. Consequently, educators undergo training and education to deliver the prescribed curriculum, with the expectation that this will foster their development into distinctive individuals and productive societal members. In this context, the assessment of teachers' professional development and their capacity to achieve educational objectives is significantly contingent upon their demonstrated performance.. As a result, it is evident that up to 95.83% of the teachers received a "Very Satisfactory" performance rating, which is a sign of steady competency in student involvement, classroom management and coordination, and instructional delivery.

Additionally, according to DepEd Memo No. 008, S. 2023, the Department of Education (2023) holds that raising professional standards for teacher development is crucial to raising student achievement and that more funding for continuing professional development will result in more highly qualified teachers who will give more students excellent learning outcomes. The teacher whose rating was "Outstanding" (4.17%) demonstrates the relationship to instructional performance. Teachers should be encouraged to understand how to take responsibility for their actions, grow as professionals, and become lifelong learners.

Therefore, educators who demonstrate strong classroom management, effective teaching methods, and positive student involvement often receive "Very Satisfactory" and "Outstanding" performance evaluations.

Area of Specialization. Table 6 shows the area of specialization of the respondents.

Table 6 Respondents' Area of Specialization

Area of Specialization	Frequency (n=24)	Percentage (100%)
English	12	50
Mathematics	4	16.67
Science	1	4.17
Filipino	1	4.17
Araling Panlipunan	3	12.5
ESP	1	4.17
TLE	1	4.17
MAPEH	1	4.17
TOTAL	24	100

Table 6 illustrates the profile of the teacher-respondents based on their area of specialization. It can be inferred that English teachers made up the biggest percentage, comprising 12 or 50%, followed by Math teachers with a frequency of 4 or 16.67%, and social studies teachers with a frequency of 3 or 12.5%. The remaining four specializations, such as Science, Filipino, ESP, TLE, and MAPEH, represent roughly identical numbers of responders of 4.17%. This shows that the majority of ARAL teachers in the two districts teach language-based subjects, with a small percentage teaching other subject.

Many studies have shown that English teachers are very important for helping students become good readers and achieve good literacy outcomes in many settings, like the ARAL reading intervention program, by working directly with each child who needs help with reading. Students in all grades will do better in reading if their teachers are clear about how to use reading techniques, know a lot about how language works, and are good at teaching reading comprehension. Literacy success depends on knowing a lot about reading in a particular area (Springer et al., 2023-02).

Furthermore, Gallagher et al. (2023) cited that studies of both multilingual and remedial reading indicate that teachers who use good instructional practices, including but not limited to modeling, scaffolding, and integrating the teaching of reading across content areas, will positively predict the engagement and competence of their students in reading. Because they know a lot about the English language and how to teach it, English-specialized teachers are the best people to set up and run reading interventions. This is because their subject knowledge gives them the tools to deal with reading problems in students in a structured way and to change their lessons based on each student's needs, with the goal of improving literacy outcomes for all students.

Length of Service. Table 7 indicates the number of years in service of the respondents.

Table 7 Length of Service

Length of Service	Frequency (n=24)	Percentage (100%)
21 years and above	6	25
16-20 years	-	-
11-15 years	5	20.83
6-10 years	8	33.34
1-5 years	5	20.83
Total	24	100
Average	11.75	-
Standard Deviation	7.41	-

Table 7 presents the length of service of the respondents. The data reveal that the biggest portion of the respondents has been working for 6-10 years, with a frequency of 8 or 33.34%. This is followed by the 21 years and above who make up 6 or 25% of the respondents. Then, there are 5 or 20.83% teachers who have been working for 1 to 5 years and 11 to 15 years in the Department of Education. However, none of the respondents fall within the 16 to 20 years category. This only means that the average length of service of 11.75 years indicates that the majority of the respondents are mid-career teachers. In short, many of them already have a lot of experience in the classroom. In addition, the standard deviation of 7.41 years demonstrates that the respondents have a wide range of teaching experience, wherein the group consists of both new teachers and experienced teachers.

The respondents who have been working for 6 to 10 years, which can be inferred that these teachers have gained professional stability and competence. Teachers with more years of experience demonstrate mastery of the

subject matter, excellent classroom management skills, and more efficient instructional decision-making because of their accumulated teaching experience (Kartini et al., as cited in Basuc et al., 2024). At this point, teachers in this group are already equipped with skills on how to meet the needs of different students and use different teaching methods to help them learn better.

On the other hand, the most experienced teachers are those with 21 years of experience or more. Veteran teachers possess a valuable experiences in the areas of curriculum delivery, student behavior management, and teaching methodologies that have been enhanced through years of direct classroom engagement. This aligns with the assertion of Nusi et al. (2025) that teachers who have been teaching for a long period are more skilled when it comes to managing a classroom, dealing with learners with varying needs, and planning effective learning strategies. In other words, experienced teachers can devise the finest techniques to educate based on the situation and the needs of their students. Meanwhile, some of the respondents are just beginning their careers in teaching, as evidenced by the fact that 20.83% of them have only been teaching for 1–5 years. Trazo and Peñas (2024) assert that educators with less than five years of experience exhibit greater affective and overall empathy than those with 16 to 20 years of experience. With this, younger educators may be more attuned to the emotional requirements of their students.

In summary, the teaching staff is primarily composed of experienced teachers, with a small number of newer teachers. There should be a combination of innovation and expertise to cultivate a collaborative school environment that is conducive to ongoing improvement. The instructional experiences of the teachers also have a significant and beneficial impact on students' learning abilities. Educators who have accumulated a greater amount of experience are more likely to effectively manage the learning process, adapt their teaching strategies to the requirements of their students, and provide their students with guidance that is efficient. As the duration of the teaching experience increases, students' learning abilities also improve (Nusi et al., 2025).

Highest Educational Attainment. Table 8 shows the highest educational attainment of the respondents.

Table 8 Highest Educational Attainment

Highest Educational Attainment	Frequency (n=24)	Percentage (100%)
Doctorate Degree	-	-
With Units in Doctorate Degree	2	8.33
Master's Degree	2	8.33
With units in Master's Degree	14	58.34
Bachelor's Degree	6	25
Total	24	100

Table 8 demonstrates the educational attainment of the respondents, wherein the majority of the teachers are pursuing master's degrees with a frequency of 14 or 58.43%. Of those who responded, 6 or 25% have a bachelor's degree, 2 or 8.33% have completed their master's degree, and 2 or 8.33% have completed units in a master's degree and a doctorate, respectively. Additionally, none of the respondents has completed their doctorate. This only shows that the distribution displays how many educators participate in ongoing professional development to advance their knowledge and credentials.

On this note, majority of the respondents have units in master's degree, which explains that each of them is dedicated to their personal growth and career advancements. In other words, it enables teachers to enhance their expertise in pedagogy, curriculum design, and educational leadership, thereby improving effectiveness in instruction and student learning outcomes. As mentioned by Hitka et al. (2021), professional advancement is very critical in developing and enhancing one's abilities, gaining experiences, and realizing one's full potential. It involves continuously advancing one's career through networking, professional development, and goal-setting.

According to Balanquit et al. (2023), faculty members with advanced degrees are thought to have superior teaching skills that have a direct impact on students' learning. This will lead to graduates performing better on licensing exams and being more productive. This aligns with the statement of Eacersall (2022), pursuing postgraduate study is a stimulating endeavor that can result in a variety of beneficial results. It can help you build higher-level thinking, writing, and research abilities; expand your earning potential, knowledge, and expertise; progress your career; and provide networking possibilities with like-minded people that are priceless for both your personal and professional life. Professional skill improvement, more job possibilities, and personal development are the main advantages of postgraduate education.

This demonstrates that teachers are eager to expand their knowledge and abilities by pursuing postgraduate studies for personal growth and professional development. As highlighted by Cruz (2024), there are many professionals who perceive education as a continuous process that goes beyond obtaining a bachelor's degree, even after starting a career. Encouraging professionals to pursue further education is crucial for gaining advanced knowledge in their field of expertise and meeting a number of demands of the workplace in the twenty-first century.

Profile of Learners. Table 9 presents the learners' profiles in the research environment with respect to age and gender.

Table 9 Age and Gender Profile

Profile	Frequency (n=242)	Percentage (100%)
Age		
17 years old	5	2.07
16 years old	22	9.09
15 years old	50	20.66
14 years old	74	30.58
13 years old	72	29.75
12 years old	19	7.85
Total	242	100
Gender		
Female	52	21.49
Male	190	78.51
Total	242	100

Table 8 shows the age and gender distribution of learner-respondents' profiles. In terms of age, the majority of the respondents are 14 years old, comprising 74 or 30.58% of the total respondents. This is followed by 13-year-old learners, with a frequency of 72 or 29.75%, and 15-year-old learners, consisting of 50 respondents or 20.66. Meanwhile, a smaller portion of the respondents fell under the age of 17, with a frequency of 5 or 2.07%, age of 12, with 19 or 7.85% respondents, and age of 16, consisting of 22 or 9.09% respondents. These findings indicate that majority of the respondents belong to 13-14 age groups which suggests that the respondents are typical junior high school learners.

According to Jean Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory, learners within these age ranges are in the formal operational stage, where adolescents acquire the capacity for abstract thought, hypothetical reasoning, and deductive reasoning.

They may now manipulate concepts, ideas, and theoretical constructs rather than being restricted to reasoning about tangible, concrete objects.

Moreover, the age range of the respondents is consistent with the Department of Education's criteria for the K-12 curriculum. According to the Republic Act No. 10533, the majority of the key stage 3 learners or the junior high school learners are between 12 and 16 years old, since the entrant age of junior high school is 12. With this, the learner-respondents in the study ranged in age from 12 to 17, which corresponds to students in Grades 7 through 10.

In terms of gender, of 244 respondents, 52 or 21.49% were females and 190 or 78.51% were males. The male respondents appear to outnumber the female ones. Social and psychological influences could account for observed disparities in learning approaches and school engagement between genders. Albert Bandura's Social Learning Theory posits that individuals acquire new behaviors and competencies through observation, interaction, and imitation within their environments. Variations in classroom dynamics and gender interactions may subsequently affect boys' and girls' levels of interest and participation in reading activities.

Furthermore, Ngongare et al. (2023) suggest that gender may impact reading comprehension outcomes, given that male and female students might exhibit differing degrees of engagement and employ distinct strategies when processing texts. These differences highlight the importance of considering gender when assessing the development of students' literacy skills and their reading proficiency.

DEGREE OF ARAL-READING PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION BASED ON ARAL SCHOOL READINESS AND RESPONSIVENESS AUDIT (ASRR)

The following tables illustrate the degree of ARAL Program implemented in terms of learners' readiness, tutor readiness, school environment readiness, parental readiness, and support system and governance readiness.

Aral Program Implementation in Terms of Learners' Readiness. Table 10 presents the extent of the ARAL program implementation in terms of learners' readiness.

Table 10 Learners' Readiness

SUBDOMAIN	INDICATOR	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Literacy and Numeracy Assessment	1.1 Were all learners assessed using CRLA, Phil-IRI, or RMA?	2.50	0.46	Fully Implemented
	1.2 Was the ARAL Learner Roster generated and validated based on assessment results?	2.41	0.50	Fully Implemented
2. Health and Nutrition	2.1 Have the targeted learners undergone the mandatory health assessment?	2.08	0.61	Partially Implemented
	2.2 Are learners tagged with health / nutrition risk (e.g., poor vision, poor hearing, undernutrition, wasting) referred?	2.08	0.72	Partially Implemented
3. Attendance and Dropout Risk	3.1 Has the school established mechanisms for following up at-risk learners (e.g., home visit, counseling)?	2.21	0.59	Partially Implemented
4. Psychosocial Support	4.1 Are counseling services readily available to ARAL Learners?	2.17	0.49	Partially Implemented
	4.2 Are learners who are emotionally at risk referred to guidance or Mental Health services?	2.08	0.46	Partially Implemented
GRAND MEAN		2.22	0.26	Partially Implemented

Legend: 2.34-3.0 Fully Implemented; 1.67-2.33 Partially Implemented; 1.0-1.66 Not Implemented

Table 10 presents the degree of ARAL program implementation in terms of learners' readiness, which reveals a grand mean of 2.22 interpreted as "Partially Implemented". This means that even though the assessment in literacy and numeracy is strongly implemented, there are parts that need to be improved, such as health services, attendance monitoring, and psychosocial support.

The results of the Literacy and Numeracy Assessment, with a mean of 2.50 and 2.46, which were interpreted as "Fully Implemented", indicate that the learners are evaluated and systematically selected for the intervention. Tatel et al. (2025) suggest that literacy screening helps identify students who might struggle with reading early on. This allows for timely interventions, which can significantly improve their reading skills. Furthermore, the adverse effects of reading disabilities and challenges on a student's academic, social, and emotional development can be addressed through early identification and support. As highlighted by Irey et al. (2025), laws directing reading screenings for all students have been introduced in response to the increasing public knowledge of reading disabilities. Various universal screening programs administer tests of targeted reading abilities for teachers to know which learners require extra help with reading.

Meanwhile, indicators under Health and Nutrition were interpreted as "Partially Implemented with a mean of 2.08. It can be inferred that not all learners have undergone consistent health assessment. As highlighted by Hamdan and Aljarrah (2024), proper nutrition helps the brain work better and learn more efficiently. Research shows that changes in diet directly affect children's thinking, behavior, and physical health, which then influences how well they do in school.

Zerga (2022) stated that one of the key causes of poor academic performance and a contributor to other problems is malnutrition. Evidence suggests that undernourishment among school-aged children increases the likelihood of chronic absenteeism, early school leavers, low enrolment, and low academic performance. Thus, this finding reveals that if learners have insufficient health support, it may limit their readiness to fully benefit from reading interventions such as ARAL program.

The findings further indicate that the Attendance and Dropout Risk mechanisms are "Partially Implemented," as evidenced by a mean score of 2.21. Consistent class attendance is a crucial determinant of academic achievement; it fosters responsibility, self-discipline, and time management abilities, all of which are essential for both personal and professional development.

Smith (2025) stated that attendance is a crucial component of students' academic journey. It is fundamental to prevent them from falling behind in their social or academic lives. Students who attend school every day are better prepared for life after school. They encounter individuals from diverse cultures, learn time management and planning skills, and develop into decent citizens. Additionally, Chronic absenteeism, as noted by Kearney et al. (2022), is strongly linked to poorer reading skills and lower academic performance. Their results show that methods for ongoing monitoring and early intervention are necessary to avoid learning gaps. Thus, making ARAL's attendance follow-up mechanisms stronger may make the program work better.

Similarly, the indicators of Psychosocial Support received a "Partially Implemented" rating with means of 2.17 and 2.08. Therefore, incorporating emotional support and mental health services into school programs is crucial. Research by Qarni et al. (2023) shows that social support is important for maintaining self-esteem, helping people cope with stress, and reducing mental health issues by improving their ability to handle life's challenges when they have strong social support. This is supported by Paredes and Ranque's (2024) study, which found that Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) in schools have been effective and beneficial for students. Students who participated in these programs demonstrate a high level of psychosocial preparation, meaning they are emotionally, socially, and mentally equipped.

The "Partially Implemented" grand mean indicates that the ARAL Program has effective evaluation methods; however, there should be a required further enhancement for its overall support mechanisms, specifically in health, attendance monitoring, and psychosocial services. The results suggest that improving multi-sectoral partnerships within the ARAL Program will enhance learners' overall readiness and maximize its impact on reading proficiency. Aligning program implementation with current evidence-based practices will help achieve the goal of producing functionally literate learners. In a study conducted by Dunn et al. (2022), it was found that the development of literacy in at-risk learners is significantly improved when schools, families, and community partners provide support for the academic interventions. The research emphasized the importance of integrated educational and support services in reducing the barriers to learning, thereby improving the literacy outcomes of struggling readers.

Aral Program Implementation in Terms of Tutors' Readiness. Table 11 presents the extent of the ARAL program implementation in terms of tutors' readiness.

Table 11 Tutors' Readiness

SUBDOMAIN	INDICATOR	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Tutor Identification and Eligibility	1.1 Has the school identified a sufficient number of tutors from eligible sources (teachers, parateachers, preservice teachers, volunteers) ?	2.54	0.51	Fully Implemented
	1.2 Are tutors selected based on prescribed criteria (e.g., learner load, subject fit, prior training, and experience)?	2.33	0.70	Partially Implemented
2. Tutor Training and Certification	2.1 Have tutors completed the required ARAL training modules (e.g., tutorial strategies, use of CRLA/Phi I-IRI/RMA data)?	2.08	0.65	Partially Implemented
3. Tutor Deployment	Is there a documented deployment plan with assigned learners, session times, and subject focus per tutor?	2.38	0.58	Fully Implemented
4. Tutor Workload and Incentives	4.1 Is the tutorial workload integrated in the teacher's or tutor's class/program load without overburdening?	2.71	0.46	Fully Implemented
	4.2 Are provisions for incentives (e.g., allowance, recognition, training credits) in place?	1.92	0.28	Partially Implemented
5. Class Program and Materials	5.1 Is there a structured class program with time blocks, groupings, and activities per week?	2.38	0.58	Fully Implemented

6. LAC, Peer Support, and Collaborative Expertise	6.1 Are teaching practices, materials, or learner strategies shared among tutors?	2.42	0.58	Fully Implemented
GRAND MEAN		2.34	0.36	Fully Implemented

Legend: 2.34-3.0 Fully Implemented; 1.67-2.33 Partially Implemented; 1.0-1.66 Not Implemented

Table 11 shows the degree of the ARAL program implementation in terms of tutors' readiness, with a grand mean of 2.34. The "Fully Implemented" interpretation indicates that the aspects of tutor readiness, such as tutor identification, deployment, workload management, and collaborative support, are effectively accomplished and carried out. However, there are other components, including tutor selection, training completion, and incentives, that need to be strengthened. This conclusion shows that the program has set up ways for tutors to get involved, but some of the support and preparation systems needed for effective tutoring still need to be enhanced. It ensures that the tutors are prepared to give the learners in the ARAL Program the best instructional support.

The findings for Tutor Identification and Eligibility imply that schools have identified a sufficient number of tutors from eligible groups, including volunteers, preservice teachers, and teachers. Consequently, this indicator is interpreted as a "Fully Implemented" rating with a 2.54 mean, which suggests that schools recognize the importance of utilizing human resources such as teachers to facilitate literacy interventions. Conversely, the indicator for selecting a tutor according to established criteria was interpreted as "Partially Implemented" with a 2.33 mean. This implies that in some situations, the selection procedure may not match the standards for requirements, experience, or prior training. As stated by Glomo (2020), tutoring is a formal process in which a more experienced and knowledgeable individual assists a less experienced and knowledgeable individual in their personal and professional development. It involves coaching, assessing, facilitating, sponsoring, supporting, guiding, and role modeling. It also encompasses certain interpersonal dynamics, such as student empowerment, career development, personal connection, trust, and support. In other words, it is very crucial to select the eligible teachers with appropriate competencies to become tutors to maximize the effectiveness of an intervention or program.

Meanwhile, the indicator for Tutor Training and Certification was also interpreted as "Partially Implemented," with a mean of 2.08, indicating that not all instructors have satisfactorily completed the mandatory ARAL training modules. It is very evident that training is essential for a tutor to be prepared, as it provides them with the necessary skills to comprehend assessments, teaching strategies, and methods to assist students who need help and guidance. Ikram (2020) mentioned that educating teachers enhances their productivity and improves student performance in academic settings. Effective training equips teachers with the needed information, skills, and competencies necessary to excel, enabling all students to perform at their highest potential. As highlighted by Hafeez (2021), training is a way to acquire the necessary abilities for a specific subject. The training is an effective method for teachers to enhance their teaching proficiency, in which a qualified teacher possesses enhanced abilities and approaches that help pupils achieve better academic outcomes. The findings show that the preparation of teacher training directly affects the quality of instructional support to struggling readers.

Moreover, the indicator for Tutor Deployment was interpreted as Fully Implemented with a mean of 2.38, indicating that schools have crafted and developed strategies for the deployment of tutors. These strategies include the subject concentration of tutors, the schedules for their sessions with students, and their assigned classes. With this, the tutoring services are efficiently coordinated and easily accessible to the appropriate students as a result of effective deployment planning. Mariño and Saluria (2025) stress that the tutorial system is centered on the teaching of individuals, wherein there is a personalized plan provided to each learner, ensuring that they feel appreciated and valued. This constructively fosters their development. When teachers as tutors are utilized appropriately and led by personalized learning plans, students receive more concentrated attention, which enhances their academic development and motivation. Kortecamp and Peters (2024) found that tutoring programs with systematically allocated tutors, consistent session schedules, and planned instructional strategies resulted in significant gains in beginning readers' reading abilities. This demonstrates that properly considering how to deploy tutors not only enhances program quality but also allows students to learn more effectively.

Furthermore, the findings indicate that Tutor Workload and Incentives have mixed results. The ability for teachers or tutors to incorporate tutorial work within their standard classwork was regarded as "Fully Implemented" with a mean of 2.71. It can be gleaned that schools can integrate tutoring responsibilities into their

current teaching loads without excessively burdening tutors. The provision of incentives to the tutors, such as allowances, recognition, or credits for professional growth, was interpreted as “Partially Implemented” with a mean of 1.91. In short, incentives and professional recognition play a critical role in sustaining motivation and delivering the effectiveness of the program. Karim et al. (2023) emphasize the significance of offering incentives, in which they discovered that incentives had a substantial and positive impact on employee performance. In addition, Priatmoko and Ahsani (2024) highlighted that a disproportionate workload, particularly those that exceed a moderate level, will have a negative impact on stress, such as minimal job dissatisfaction.

Additionally, the indicator under the Class Program and Materials was interpreted as “Fully implemented” with a mean of 2.38, which means that the school has a structured tutoring plan with time blocks, groupings, and activities per week. This means that the tutoring sessions are planned in a systematic and organized way to ensure that the program is delivered effectively. Cayabyab (2023) stressed the need to establish a schedule for the reading program following each lesson to enhance the learners' reading skills. Likewise, Adipu et al (2023) identified several strategies to enhance students' reading comprehension: parental and teacher motivation, fostering a culture of reading within the school, awarding children who demonstrate a passion for reading, and providing engaging literature. These findings suggest that one effective method to enhance students' reading comprehension is through the creation of engaging learning materials.

On the other hand, the indicator for LAC, Peer Support, and Collaborative Expertise was interpreted as Fully Implemented with a mean of 2.42, which indicates that the teachers are collaborating with each other. This means that they are exchanging methodologies, resources, and techniques to guide and assist the learners. According to Magundayao (2024), the Department of Education (DepEd) has emphasized the significance of ongoing professional development for educators to enhance the quality of education in the Philippines. A notable project in this regard is the Learning Action Cell (LAC), a school-based, teacher-led learning group aimed at promoting professional development and improving the teaching-learning process. In accordance with the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013, or Republic Act No. 10533, the Department of Education (DepEd) promulgated the policy on Learning Action Cells (LAC) as a component of the K–12 Basic Education Program (DepEd Order No. 35, 2016). LAC is regarded as a significant professional development technique aimed at enhancing teaching practices by establishing a collaborative platform for educators to exchange best practices, tackle teaching issues, and expand their understanding of diverse pedagogical methods.

In summary, the Fully Implemented grand mean demonstrates that, while the ARAL Program has some positive aspects in terms of tutor readiness, it needs to focus more on tutor selection, completing required training modules, providing incentives, and ensuring that all instructional materials and programs are consistent. The ARAL Program has put in place certain procedures to encourage tutors to get interested and contribute, but the training and reward systems, as well as the program design, should be enhanced to make the program more efficient.

Aral Program Implementation in Terms of School Environment Readiness. Table 12 presents the extent of the ARAL program implementation in terms of school environment readiness.

Table 12 School Environment Readiness

SUBDOMAIN	INDICATOR	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Physical Learning Space (ARAL ROOM)	1.1 Is there a designated ARAL Room or space (ventilated, well-lit, quiet)?	2.17	0.64	Partially Implemented
	1.2 Is adequate school furniture available and functional?	2.42	0.65	Fully Implemented
2. Sanitation and Hygiene Facilities	2.1 Does the school meet the basic requirements and standards for sanitation in line with the WinS Three-Star Approach	2.04	0.62	Partially Implemented
	2.2. Are learners provided access to safe drinking water?	2.08	0.58	Partially Implemented
	2.3 Are there visible hygiene promotion materials in learning areas (e.g., handwashing posters, campaign reminders)?	1.96	0.69	Partially Implemented

3. Learning and Teaching Resources	3.1 Are ARAL teaching guides, workbooks, and remedial modules available for learners and tutors?	2.38	0.58	Fully Implemented
	3.2 Do learners have sufficient access to textbooks, print modules, or digital LMS?	2.42	0.58	Fully Implemented
4. Access to Technology and Power	4.1 Are digital devices (laptops / desktops) accessible for tutorials or assessments?	2.13	0.68	Partially Implemented
	4.2 Is electricity available and stable during ARAL implementation?	2.50	0.59	Fully Implemented
5. Connectivity and ICT Readiness	5.1 Does the internet connection meet the following requirements: a. Download speed: ≥ 40 mbps b. Upload speed: ≥ 12 Mbps c. Latency: $800 \leq ms$	1.96	0.55	Partially Implemented
	5.2 Network Stress Test (50 participants accessing content simultaneously): Were participants able to access smoothly?	1.79	0.72	Partially Implemented
	5.3 Does the school have sufficient computers/laptops for ARAL use (1:1 ideal, 1:5 max)?	1.96	0.55	Partially Implemented
	5.4 Does the school have computer rooms?	2.17	0.70	Partially Implemented
6. Equity and Protection Enablers	6.1 Is there an active Child Protection Committee (CPC) organized and functioning in the school?	2.13	0.74	Partially Implemented
	6.2 Is there an established mechanism for reporting and monitoring bullying/ abuse cases affecting ARAL learners?	2.04	0.69	Partially Implemented
GRAND MEAN		2.14	0.39	Partially Implemented

Legend: 2.34-3.0 Fully Implemented; 1.67-2.33 Partially Implemented; 1.0-1.66 Not Implemented

Table 12 shows the ARAL program implementation in terms of school environment readiness, where the grand mean is 2.14, interpreted as “Partially Implemented”. The result further displays that the majority of the indicators for School Environment Readiness are classified as “Partially Implemented”, while only a small number are identified as “Fully Implemented”. This demonstrates that schools are making their way to improve their facilities, learning materials, and utilities. However, there are still areas of the school environment and infrastructure that need improvement since these components are very important to the success of ARAL program activities.

The findings of the subdomain Physical Learning Space indicate a “Partially Implemented” status with a mean of 2.17 in terms of designated ARAL rooms that are quiet, well-lit, and well-ventilated. This means that there are appropriate learning spaces in school, but these are not adequate to support all learners during the intervention. Moreover, the adequacy of functional school furniture gained a 2.42 weighted mean interpreted as “Fully Implemented”. This suggests that the chairs, tables, and other basic classroom furniture are sufficient and functional. As mentioned by Dalimunthe et al. (2024), a positive and effective learning environment significantly increases student motivation and engagement in the learning process. Students who have a conducive environment to learn are more motivated to engage in educational activities. Additionally, conducive learning spaces provide the attainment of educational objectives effectively and efficiently, as a supportive culture fosters an optimal learning process for each individual within the school setting (Qureshi et al., 2023).

Furthermore, in terms of Sanitation and Hygiene Facilities, the results signify that all indicators are interpreted as “Partially Implemented” such as compliance with sanitation standards with a mean of 2.04, access to safe drinking water with a mean of 2.08, and the availability of hygiene promotion materials with a mean of 1.96. This implies that although sanitation standards exist, they are not consistently upheld in all schools. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), The right to education and water and sanitation for children are fundamental human rights that cannot be taken away or compromised. Children are entitled to a safe and sustainable learning environment that includes simple access to water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) services.

Attendance and educational achievement in schools may be negatively affected by inadequate access to WASH facilities.

In terms of Learning and Teaching Resources, the indicators were interpreted as “Fully Implemented”, as shown by the availability of ARAL teaching guides, workbooks, and remedial modules with a weighted mean of 2.38, and sufficient access to textbooks and digital learning materials with a weighted mean of 2.42. This implies that schools are equipped with instructional learning resources that are needed to support the ARAL program. William (2025) stressed that schools with sufficient resources, such as current textbooks, workbooks, and access to digital learning platforms, have higher literacy outcomes. Conversely, schools with limited resources demonstrated low literacy achievement levels. Educators in resource-abundant schools were more adept at employing varied teaching techniques, enhancing the learning experience for of the learners. Kapur (2019), as cited by Somba (2022), asserts that teaching and learning resources (TLR) are instruments employed by educators in schools to enhance students' comprehension. These are the instructional resources utilized in the classroom to facilitate the learning objectives outlined in the lesson plan. Within the educational system, these TLRs have been used for years in the classroom environment.

Similarly, the subdomain of Access to Technology and Power reveals a “Partially Implemented” status with a weighted mean of 2.13 for the indicator on access to digital devices such as laptops and desktops, which indicates a limited availability of technological devices. Meanwhile, the indicator on the availability and stability of electricity obtained a weighted mean of 2.50, interpreted as “Fully Implemented”. This means that the school has a reliable power supply to support the various learning activities in the ARAL program. Bhat (2023) stated that technology enables teachers to customize learning experiences according to specific student learning speeds. Adaptive learning platforms can modify the complexity and tempo of information according to students' performance, guaranteeing that each student can have a tailored learning path. In addition, according to the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), technology cultivates immersive learning settings, enhances student experiences, promotes cooperation, and broadens connections. This means that utilizing technology enhances learners' motivation and engagement, making learning more enjoyable and effective.

Furthermore, all indicators under the subdomain of Connectivity and ICT Readiness, such as internet quality and speed with a 1.96 weighted mean, network stress capacity with a 1.79 weighted mean, and availability of computers and laptops with a weighted mean of 2.17, were interpreted as “Partially Implemented”. These findings suggest that the school struggles to maintain sufficient and dependable internet connectivity and ICT infrastructure, which results in problems in data management and access to online learning resources. As highlighted by Lausa et al. (2024), using information and communication technology in the classroom is crucial to achieving sustainable development through education. Similarly, Shikomera et al. (2023) stated that using the internet is the most effective technique to incorporate ICT into classroom instruction. ICT integration in education is greatly aided by infrastructure, management systems, and internet accessibility.

In addition, the indicators under the subdomain Equity and Protection Enablers were rated as “Partially Implemented”: specifically, the presence of Child Protection Committees (weighted mean of 2.13) and methods for reporting and monitoring bullying (weighted mean of 2.04). The results implied that although safety precautions are in place, they are not always implemented at every school. As a result, students perform better in school and feel better about themselves when they are in a safe, motivating learning environment. Regidor et al. (2024) asserted that a conducive learning environment creates a sense of empowerment and appreciation among learners. A conducive learning environment focuses on how learners in the class interact with each other. It encourages them to study for the future, share their thoughts, and talk to their teachers, unlike in a traditional classroom. The Department of Social Welfare and Development, as referenced by Cubio and Bagnol (2025), states that effective Child Protection Committees are important for making communities safe for children. This is done by ensuring that all parties work together, that child protection issues are addressed promptly, and that long-term solutions are put in place. The organization, resources, policy alignment, and execution of Child Protection Committees (CPCs) in schools are all important for their success.

With these findings, the School Environment Readiness subdomain signifies that certain indicators, such as electricity and teaching materials, are satisfactory; however, additional efforts are required to develop sanitation and protection and containment measures, ICT, and institutional protective measures.

Aral Program Implementation in Terms of Parental Readiness. Table 13 presents the extent of the ARAL program implementation in terms of parental readiness.

Table 13 Parental Readiness

SUBDOMAIN	INDICATOR	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. Parental Consent and Commitment	1.1 Have all identified ARAL learners submitted signed parent/guardian consent forms?	2.33	0.76	Partially Implemented
	1.2 Are parents/guardians aware and fully oriented of their child's inclusion in ARAL?	1.92	0.88	Partially Implemented
	1.3 Are parents/guardians aware of their role in the ARAL implementation?	2.04	0.75	Partially Implemented
2. PTA and Parent Education Programs	2.1 Has the PTA supported ARAL implementation (e.g., volunteers, facilitators, monitoring)?	2.17	0.70	Partially Implemented
	2.2 Has the school conducted orientation or parenting education sessions to support ARAL at home?	1.96	0.62	Partially Implemented
3. Home School Collaboration	3.1 Is there a system to track parent—teacher communication on learner progress (e.g., text, chat group, FB community)?	2.08	0.72	Partially Implemented
	3.2 Are learners receiving support at home?	1.96	0.62	Partially Implemented
GRAND MEAN		2.07	0.63	Partially Implemented

Legend: 2.34-3.0 Fully Implemented; 1.67-2.33 Partially Implemented; 1.0-1.66 Not Implemented

Table 13 displays the degree of ARAL program implementation in terms of Parental Readiness with a grand mean of 2.07, which is interpreted as “Partially Implemented”. The results suggest that all indicators related to parental readiness are classified as “Partially Implemented,” indicating that the ARAL Program has not yet thoroughly demonstrated the engagement, awareness, and participation of parents. This means that although schools have initiated efforts to engage parents through asking their consent, collaborating with the Parent-Teachers Association, and creating platforms to communicate with each other, these tasks are not consistently completed.

In terms of the subdomain Parental Commitment and Agreement, the findings demonstrate that it is “Partially Implemented”; specifically, the indicators such as parents signed consent papers got a weighted mean of 2.33, knew their child was part of the ARAL program obtained a weighted mean of 1.92, and parents were aware of their role in the program got a weighted mean of 2.04. The results exhibit that although some parents comply with their obligations, such as giving permission, they still don’t have enough knowledge about the program and their responsibilities to support their child in the ARAL program. Ahmad (2024) stated that students' academic success is significantly determined by parental involvement. Students who have supportive parents tend to have higher academic achievements and goals than those who do not. Additionally, it can be manifested in various ways such as providing materials, guiding with their assignments, volunteering, and communicating with their children themselves. The results from the study of Kantova (2024) confirm the established positive correlation between high school graduation and parental involvement. The results of the analysis suggest that the probability of high school graduation is higher for children who have a higher level of non-school-related parental involvement. This suggests that a child's educational outcomes can be significantly influenced by their active participation in activities beyond academics.

The indicators of the subdomain PTA and Parent Education Programs show a “Partially Implemented” rating; specifically, on the PTA support for ARAL implementation, with a weighted mean of 2.17, and the conduct of orientation or parenting education sessions to support ARAL at home, with a weighted mean of 1.96. This implies that while there is an involvement of PTA, it is not enough to support the program to achieve its intended results. Vinita (2025) stressed that

Parent-Teacher Associations (PTAs) are very important to create a positive learning environment through facilitating interaction between teachers and parents. They play a crucial role in fostering collaboration, which would result in improved educational policies, resource utilization, and student performance. This aligns with the study of Rudin (2025) that parents can contribute to the enhancement of the quality and effectiveness of schools. He further emphasized that parental participation significantly impacts not only student achievement but also the educational environment and instructional methods. Engagement in the PTA, resource mobilization, regular

communication, and the formulation of common goals among stakeholders foster a supportive learning atmosphere, ultimately improving teacher morale, motivation, and efficacy.

Meanwhile, the indicators for the subdomain Home School Collaboration display a “Partially Implemented” rating; specifically, the indicator on a system to track parent-teacher communication on learners’ progress received a weighted mean of 2.08, and the indicator on learners’ support received at home obtained a weighted mean of 1.96. This suggests that the schools may already have a message system or community groups for communication, though these are not designed to promote active collaboration. The lack of support at home suggests that parents may not be adequately engaged in helping their children improve their reading beyond school hours. Rudin (2025) states that one of the approaches to improving school education is to encourage parents and the community to collaborate with the school to develop a plan. Parents should not merely provide encouragement and assistance to their children at home; they should also be regarded as active partners in fostering their academic success.

Thus, the ARAL program's parental readiness is still a work in progress. Although there are some signs of improvement, such as securing agreement and involving parents in some capacity, the school still needs parents to be more interested and cooperative in their children's activities. Moreover, there should be a robust communication system and parent education programs to encourage more parents to guide their children's reading development.

Aral Program Implementation in Terms of Support System and Governance Readiness. Table 14 presents the extent of the ARAL program implementation in terms of support system and governance readiness.

Table 14 Support System and Governance Readiness

SUBDOMAIN	INDICATOR	Weighted Mean	SD	Interpretation
1. School Governance Support	1.1 Is ARAL included in the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and MOOE budget allocations?	2.17	0.76	Partially Implemented
	1.2 Is the School Governance Council (SGC) engaged in ARAL implementation?	1.92	0.78	Partially Implemented
2. Local Government Unit (LGU) Support	2.1 Has the Local School Board (LSB) allocated Special Education Fund (SEP) or passed resolutions to support ARAL needs?	1.63	0.77	Partially Implemented
	2.2 Has the LGU issued local ordinances, executive orders, or inter-agency support mechanisms related to ARAL?	1.75	0.74	Partially Implemented
3. Technical Assistance & Monitoring	3.1 Has the Division/ Regional Office provided coaching, mentoring, or feedback to the school on ARAL program planning and preparation?	2.38	0.71	Fully Implemented
4. Capacity Building	4.1 Have school heads, nonteaching personnel, and focal persons received formal capacity development from DepEd, Higher Education Institutions (HEIS) , or Non-government Organizations (NGOs)?	2.17	0.64	Partially Implemented
5. Multi Sectoral Partnerships	5.1. Are there active partnerships with private orgs, academe, NGOs, or Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) supporting ARAL?	1.67	0.76	Partially Implemented
6. Non-Teaching Personnel Deployment	6.1 Has the SDO/ school designated an Administrative Officer/ Project Development Officer (AO/PDO) (deployed by DepEd Human Resource Division) to assist in ARAL coordination?	2.08	0.78	Partially Implemented
GRAND MEAN		1.97	0.57	Partially Implemented

Legend: 2.34-3.0 Fully Implemented; 1.67-2.33 Partially Implemented; 1.0-1.66 Not Implemented

Table 14 illustrates the ARAL Program's implementation in terms of Support System and Governance Readiness, with the overall mean of 1.97, indicating that the program is "Partially Implemented." The findings imply that the majority of the indicators under the subdomain Governance and Support Mechanism are “Partially

Implemented". This suggests that schools have frameworks and initiatives in place to support the ARAL Program. However, these are not yet fully established or consistently functional at all levels. The findings indicate that School Governance Support is "Partially Implemented."

In the area of School Governance and Support, the integration of ARAL into the School Improvement Plan (SIP) and the Maintenance and Other Operating Expenses (MOOE) budget received a weighted mean score of 2.17. In contrast, the involvement of the School Governance Council (SGC) yielded a weighted mean of 1.92. The results indicate that although ARAL is recognized in school planning and budgeting, the level of governance participation remains moderate. Sustainable program management requires school governance bodies to show more commitment and involvement.

Good school operations require a diverse group of people to be involved in making decisions. Democratizing school governance has become a crucial element of contemporary educational reform. Enad (2025) posits that the adoption of inclusive and participatory approaches enhances both the perceived legitimacy and the practical effectiveness of educational institutions. The School Governing Council (SGC), a body comprising essential stakeholders such as educators, parents, community members, school administrators, and local government representatives, is designed to collectively address the specific requirements of each school. This framework was instituted in the Philippines through DepEd Order No. 26, s.2022.

Nabus and Homillano (2025) posit that school governing councils (SGCs) play a crucial role in supporting, advising, and guiding school administrators in the formulation of strategies aimed at enhancing educational standards. The implementation of shared governance structures within SGCs is essential to address the diverse needs of students and the specific circumstances of the community, all while remaining compliant with national regulations.

The indicators also suggest that the subdomain Local Government Unit (LGU) Support is "Partially Implemented." The weighted mean for allocating the Special Education Fund (SEF) or passing resolutions in support of ARAL was 1.63. Meanwhile, the weighted mean for issuing municipal ordinances or interagency support mechanisms was 1.75. These data show that local government partners provide moderate financial and policy assistance to ARAL. A study conducted by UNICEF demonstrated that schools could generate the most proficient learners, regardless of their minimal resources, provided that they receive the assistance of local officials and community members. As mentioned by Adao and Ching (2024), we can improve student performance and foster community development by enhancing the partnership between educational institutions and local government officials. Educational institutions and local government units can collaborate to develop initiatives and programs that address community needs, such as facilitating access to education and promoting health and well-being.

Additionally, the Technical Assistance and Monitoring subdomain has a "Fully Implemented" rating, with a weighted mean of 2.38. The result indicates that the Division or Regional Office has been consistently providing schools with coaching, mentorship, and feedback. The presence of technical assistance reveals that supervisors are effectively guiding the teachers, which is crucial for enhancing program planning and implementation. As stated by Ogusanju (2006) and cited by Honculada (2022), the primary objective of supervision is to guide the teachers in enhancing their pedagogical skills and students' learning experience. Instructional leaders equip the teachers with the skills to implement the education system's vision and mission, enabling them to perform their duties more effectively.

The results suggest that the subdomain Capacity Building got a weighted mean of 2.17, interpreted as "Partially Implemented". This reveals that although certain schools, non-teaching personnel, and focal persons have received training from DepEd, HEIs, or NGOs, the capacity development programs are either ongoing or not comprehensive enough. Continuous professional education is essential to equip the teachers who serve as the implementers of the ARAL program. According to Werimba (2024), capacity building is intended to enhance the effectiveness of classroom teachers through giving them the necessary information and skills to deliver effective lessons, as well as improved teaching strategies, techniques, and new teaching materials. Teachers who have undergone capacity building for the ARAL program gained valuable insights and skills for its implementation.

The Multi-Sectoral Partnerships subdomain is classified as "Partially Implemented," which obtained a weighted mean of 1.67. The result indicates that the enterprises, educational institutions, NGOs, and civil society organizations have minimal active engagement supporting the ARAL program. These partnerships are crucial for increasing program participation, augmenting resources, and amplifying advocacy. According to Wango et

al. (2025), multi-sectoral partnerships facilitate the establishment of relationships between educational institutions and their surrounding communities. Schools and students' educational experiences may be improved through the involvement of business, parents, and the community, which would result to an increased number of individuals to contribute to the improvement of education.

Lastly, the subdomain Deployment of Non-Teaching Staff had a weighted mean of 2.08, indicating "Partially Implemented." The result shows the presence of Administrative Officers or Project Development Officers (AO/PDO) assisting with ARAL coordination, their performance may not be optimized. If there are support personnel, it can significantly enhance coordination, documentation, and oversight of the program. According to the Department of Education, hiring administrative support personnel is crucial to create a smooth school operation and reducing the workload of the teachers and for them to focus on teaching and supervision. These staff members assist with administrative and coordination duties, thereby improving the program's overall operations. According to Bucoy and Punzalan's (2025) study, non-teaching staff play an important part in managing school administration tasks, although they usually face challenges that make it difficult for them to perform their tasks properly, such as insufficient training, inadequate support, or a lack of understanding of their responsibilities. These challenges may make it difficult for them to use their positions to effectively put educational goals into practice.

Overall, the findings suggest that while the higher office provides sufficient technical assistance, there is a need to improve various governance aspects, including sectoral integration, multisectoral collaboration, capacity development, and engagement with local government units. The ARAL Program is presently improving its governance preparedness and support framework. Thus, it is very important to broaden the various collaboration and partnerships among stakeholders to achieve the full implementation and long-term sustainability of ARAL program.

Summary on the Degree of the ARAL Program Implementation. Table 16 presents the degree of the ARAL program implementation in terms on the readiness of learners, tutors, school environment, parents, and support system and governance

Table 15 Summary on the Degree of the ARAL Program Implementation

Items	Weighted Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
Learners' Readiness	2.22	0.26	Partially Implemented
Tutors' Readiness	2.34	0.36	Fully Implemented
School Environment Readiness	2.14	0.39	Partially Implemented
Parental Readiness	2.07	0.63	Partially Implemented
System Support and Governance Readiness	1.97	0.57	Partially Implemented
GRAND MEAN	2.15	0.14	Partially Implemented

Legend: 2.34-3.00 Fully Implemented; 1.67-2.33 Partially Implemented; 1.00-1.66 Not Implemented

Table 15 exhibits the consolidated view of the degree of the ARAL Program implementation across five key domains such as Learners' Readiness, Tutors' Readiness, School Environment Readiness, Parental Readiness, and Support System and Governance Readiness with a grand mean of 2.15 interpreted as "Partially Implemented". This means that the program is working in important areas, but it hasn't been fully optimized yet and needs to be strengthened in order to reach its goals.

Tutors' Readiness got the highest weighted mean of 2.34 among the five domains which in interpreted as "Fully Implemented," indicating that tutors are well-prepared for deployment, teaching duties, and working with others. This means the program has successfully established mechanisms to ensure tutors can help students learn. Casinto (2025) supports this finding by stating that professional training and being prepared to teach, which includes using ICT and the appropriate tactics, are both critical for increasing student engagement and comprehension. Similarly, findings by Gagabe et al. (2024) and Berry (2024) on the National Learning Camp (NLC) show that well qualified educators improve literacy and academic performance.

On the other hand, the lowest mean was for System Support and Governance Readiness with a weighted mean of 1.97, indicating issues with administrative support, coordination, and policy execution. This suggests that, while the program is in existence at the school level, there are still issues with monitoring systems, technical assistance, and resource use. This is consistent with the findings of Abad and Vargus (2024), who discovered

that program implementation issues, such as a lack of time, resources, or organized support systems, can significantly affect the effectiveness of intervention programs like NLC. Additionally, as stated by William et al. (2025), government-led initiatives frequently fail when there is insufficient institutional backing or teacher preparation.

Parental Readiness with a weighted mean of 2.07 is interpreted as “Partially Implemented,” with a high standard deviation, indicating that parents are not always involved. This supports Casinto (2025) assertion that parents play a critical role in implementing literacy programs, particularly in promoting learners' emotional and behavioral development. Furthermore, he emphasized that learners' motivation and their reading skills are reinforced through continuous practice outside the classroom, facilitated by parental involvement and home support.

The School Environment Readiness obtained a weighted mean of 2.14 which shows limited implementation, suggesting that while schools provide some assistance, learning conditions and resources have not yet been fully maximized. According to Adapon and Mangila (2020), learners may find it more difficult to learn to read if they don't have enough resources and teachers don't provide enough assistance. Additionally, many Philippine schools continue to face challenges that prevent programs from being implemented effectively, such as inadequate buildings and instructional resources.

Learners' Readiness obtained a weighted mean of 2.22 which is interpreted as “Partially Implemented” in the ARAL Program. This indicates that learners are academically prepared for ARAL sessions, but their overall readiness, including well-being and emotional support, is inconsistent. Moreover, these areas should be strengthened to make sure that learners get the most out of the program. According to Nailon et al. (2023), students who are struggling with reading need extra assistance and especially in the upper grades where reading becomes more difficult. Similarly, Fernando and Ambayon (2024) emphasized that reading comprehension is the core of the learners' reading processes wherein if students lack strong core skills, they may struggle to achieve proficiency.

In summary, the findings show that, while tutor readiness is an ARAL Program strength, its full implementation is hampered by a lack of system support, family involvement, school resources, and learner readiness. This supports the results of Bitanes and Estera (2025) and Salibay (2024), which state that the effectiveness of reading interventions depends on the collaborative efforts of teachers, parents, schools, and the community. Even well-prepared teachers may struggle to make the most of the program if they do not receive adequate support.

Learners' Reading Achievement. Table 16 presents the learners' reading achievement through the ARAL program.

Table 16 Learners' Reading Achievement

Reading Level	Code	Frequency (n=242)	Percentage (100%)	Code x Frequency
Frustration	1	58	23.97	58
Instructional	2	173	71.49	346
Independent	3	11	4.54	33
Total	-	242	100	437
Mean	-	-	-	1.81

Legend: 2.34-3.00 Independent; 1.67-2.33 Instructional; 1.00-1.66 Frustration

Table 9 illustrates the learners' reading achievement after the ARAL program implementation based on the administered PHIL-IRI. The results revealed that the majority of the learners fell under the instructional level, comprising 173 or 71.49% of the total population. At this level, the learners needed a little assistance in reading and showed minimal comprehension. However, there are 58 or 23.97% learners who belonged to the frustration level, which indicates that learners in this level were struggling to read and have little or no comprehension at all. Meanwhile, there are 11 or 4.54% learners who are proficient readers and classified as independent, which indicates learners can read fluently and understand the text on their own. In addition, the computed mean score of 1.81 is within the range of 1.67 to 2.33 for instructional reading. This shows that the learners' total reading achievement is at the instructional level following the implementation of the ARAL Program. This indicates that many students have improved their reading skills, but more work is still required to enable more students to become proficient readers on their own.

Learners who fall under the frustration level suggest that they experience difficulty in reading and understanding the text. Learners at this stage encounter difficulties with word recognition, reading fluency, and comprehension. Balansag (2025) emphasizes that a student's literacy journey experiences a critical juncture during the intermediate grades, where reading fluency becomes essential for achievement across diverse subjects. Those operating at the frustration level face challenges in word decoding, maintaining reading pace, and articulating their thoughts effectively. These challenges not only undermine their self-assurance and interest in reading but also hinder their ability to grasp academic content. Learners who were classified in instructional level reveal that most learners can read with guidance but still require the assistance of the teacher to improve their comprehension and fluency. This result confirms the findings of Ehri's (2020) study, which highlighted that learners progressively advance from assisted reading to independent reading ability. The research indicates that students improve their reading skills by learning the connection between letters and sounds, and by frequently practicing word recognition until they can recognize words independently. In order to achieve independent reading, students must develop their decoding and comprehension skills, which are strengthened by such instructional support.

Thus, the ARAL Program is crucial in helping students advance from the frustration level to the instructional level. Intensive literacy interventions and ongoing reading support are still required to improve the number of students who can achieve the independent reading level.

TESTING SIGNIFICANT RELATIONSHIPS

Degree of Implementation of the ARAL Program Implementation and Key Stage 3 Learners' Reading Achievement. Table 17 discloses the results of testing the relationship between the degree of the ARAL program implementation readiness and Key Stage 3 learners' academic achievement

Table 17 Testing of Significant Relationships

Variables	Computed r	Critical p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Degree of Implementation of the ARAL Program and Key Stage 3 Learners' Reading Achievement	0.465	0.022	Rejected	Significant

Reflected in Table 17 the degree of correlation between the degree of implementation of the ARAL program and learners' reading achievement, with a Pearson r of 0.465 and a P-value of 0.022, which was lesser than the significance level at 0.05. The result indicates that the relationship between the ARAL program implementation and learners' reading achievement is significant, which led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. The results revealed that as the implementation level of the ARAL program increases, learners' reading achievement tends to improve. Furthermore, the program's effectiveness increases when the school is sufficiently prepared for its implementation.

This agrees to the study of Berry (2024) where it was found that the National Learning Camps (NLC) have had a considerable positive influence on student learning outcomes, particularly improving reading and numeracy skills among the students. The result of the study also corroborates to the study of Graciano (2024) where The Project REACH reading intervention has a strong influence on the learners' reading comprehension skills. Based on the results, there was a considerable difference in the learners' reading comprehension skills before and after the project REACH implementation.

Moreover, Vygotsky's philosophy in social learning theory is evident in the program, for it emphasizes guided instruction, mentorship, and collaborative learning. The ARAL program provides timely, responsive, and effective support to learners who fall below the expected reading proficiency levels, enabling them to cope with the grade-level expectations set by the Department of education. Teachers, peers, and tutors act as a scaffold to help those struggling learners read better and fill in the gaps in their learning. In addition, Bloom's Mastery Learning Theory also supports the goal of the ARAL program, which is to provide structured and continuous remediation, especially in improving learners' reading proficiency levels. This allows the learners to be given focused reading activities, immediate feedback, and the opportunity to practice until such time they show they have already mastered a literacy or reading task. This approach ensures that no learners are left behind because each of them is given more time and individualized support until the learning gaps are filled.

In conclusion, the statistically significant relationship between the degree of ARAL program implementation and the learners' reading achievement reveals that the school readiness plays a crucial role in enhancing learners' reading achievement. Fernando and Ambayon (2024) discovered that a well-designed reading programs improve

student reading skills. Furthermore, Bitanes and Estera (2025) stressed that the involvement of family and community have a significant impact in improving learners' reading abilities.

4. SUMMARY, FINDINGS, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the summary, findings, conclusion, and recommendations of the study.

Summary

This study determined the relationship of implementing the Academic Recovery and Accessible Learning (ARAL) Program on the reading achievement of Key Stage 3 learners in Getafe 1 and 2 Districts during the school year 2025-2026. In addition, the purpose of this study is to evaluate the schools' readiness and responsiveness across all five domains to determine whether a correlation exists between the ARAL Program implementation and learners' reading achievement. This research employed a quantitative-correlational study with the use of a standardized questionnaire in gathering the important and relevant data to the study.

Findings

The findings revealed that the majority of the teacher respondents are mostly female, married, and in their early to middle age. They generally have graduate-level education, several years of teaching experience, and very satisfactory performance ratings.

The ARAL program is partially implemented across most domains, with tutors' readiness is the only domain rated as fully implemented, which shows that the teachers are well-prepared to instruct and support learners. Meanwhile, learners' readiness, school environment readiness, parental readiness, and system support and governance are partially implemented, which indicates that resources, student preparedness, family involvement, and stakeholders' coordination still need to be enhanced. Overall, the program is functioning, but it need to enhance some key areas for it reached its full potential.

In terms of students' reading achievement, they have improved from frustration to predominantly instructional after the implementation of ARAL program. This reveals that the majority of students are now capable of reading proficiently with the assistance and guidance of a teacher. This only demonstrates that the program has helped and enhanced reading abilities of the learners, although only a small number of them were able to read independently. Nevertheless, additional support is required to help more students achieve full reading proficiency.

Moreover, it is also revealed that there is a significant relationship between the degree of the ARAL Program implementation and the learners' reading achievement. This implies that as the implementation level of the ARAL program increases, learners' reading achievement also improves. Furthermore, the program's effectiveness increases when the school is sufficiently prepared for its implementation.

Conclusion

The results indicate that the ARAL Program is partially implemented which implies that the institution is moderately prepared; however, it must still implement certain modifications to strengthen the ARAL program. This demonstrated that the program is functioning in certain key areas; however, it has not yet realized its maximum potential and requires additional development. The tutors' readiness got the highest rating among the five domains, which shows that teachers are ready to instruct and assist students.

On the other hand, the weakest area is system support and governance, which indicates minor issues with administrative support and stakeholders' coordination. Additionally, the school environment, students' readiness, and parents' readiness are only partially implemented, which can be inferred that there are insufficient resources, students who are not adequately prepared, and families that are not sufficiently involved. In general, the schools are capable of implementing the program; however, it must continue to enhance its readiness and increase stakeholder involvement, resources, and support systems.

In addition, the study shows a significant relationship between the degree of ARAL program implementation and learners' reading achievement, indicating that a higher level of program implementation enhances learners' reading achievement. Likewise, the program is effective when the school is well-prepared to support its implementation.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that the school should continue strengthening its ARAL program implementation through enhancing support systems, resources, and stakeholder coordination, including parent and community involvement. There should be an ongoing professional development for the ARAL

teachers to sustain their high educational quality. At the same time, additional interventions should be provided for learners who are still struggling to read so that they can reach the instructional level and, especially, the independent level. Furthermore, the school should make sure that there is a well-prepared learning environment for ARAL learners, sufficient learning materials, and coordinated governance to maximize the program's effectiveness and help learners improve their reading achievement.

5. OUTPUT OF THE STUDY

Rationale

Reading is one of the fundamental skills that extensively influences the learners' academic success. It is a lifelong skill that improves vocabulary, better comprehension, and develops critical thinking skills. Reading enables children to independently absorb material, while teachers establish clear and sequential instructional methods. It disrupts the students' lack of interest by motivating them to engage more actively and effectively in the educational process. Therefore, employing methods that improve learners' reading comprehension is essential. Furthermore, reading comprehension is considered the fundamental element of the reading process and the primary process around which all other processes revolve. It constitutes the foundation of all reading processes and the pinnacle of reading proficiency (Fernando & Ambayon, 2024).

Schools continue to encounter several challenges, such as lack of learning resources, insufficiency of administrative support, minimal parent involvement, and varying levels of student readiness, despite the implementation of the reading programs. These factors influence the effectiveness of this program, which emphasizes that it is very crucial to assess the degree or extent of its implementation and its impact on students' reading proficiency. With this, schools can better assist learners who struggle with reading and eventually enhance their literacy skills.

Sustaining the ARAL Program is essential to ensure continuous improvement in learners' reading achievement. Moreover, well-supported programs from the teachers, administrators, parents, and other community stakeholders ensure that the school can fully implement the ARAL program effectively. Establishing a conducive learning environment and strengthening collaboration and support systems will help deliver an effective reading program. As a result, the learners are given the opportunity to receive the assistance they need to improve their reading skills.

Objectives

This enhanced ARAL Program will hopefully:

1. Strengthen learners' readiness by improving health support, attendance monitoring, and psychosocial services;
2. Enhance tutors' competencies through continuous training, proper selection, and provision of incentives;
3. Improve the school environment by providing sufficient facilities for learning, teaching resources, and ICT support;
4. Increase parental involvement through active participation, effective communication, and home-based learning support;
5. Reinforce system support and governance by strengthening coordination, partnerships, and program monitoring mechanisms; and
6. Strengthen learners' reading skills through targeted interventions, guided reading activities, and continuous assessment.

Scheme of Implementation

This scheme focuses on strengthening the implementation of the ARAL Program based on the five key domains: Learners' Readiness, Tutors' Readiness, School Environment Readiness, Parental Readiness, and Support System and Governance Readiness. It aims to enhance learners' reading skills, improve tutor competencies, optimize the school environment, increase parental involvement, and reinforce system support and governance for sustainable program outcomes.

Area of Concerns	Objectives	Strategies	Persons Involved	Budget	Budget Source	Time Frame	Evaluative Measures	Accomplishments	Remarks
Learners' Health, Attendance, and Psychosocial Support	Strengthen learners' overall readiness for reading interventions	Conduct regular health assessments, feeding programs, attendance monitoring, and counseling sessions	Teachers, school heads, health personnel, guidance counselors	Php 20,000	MOOE/School Fund	Year-round SY 2026-2027	Improved attendance, health status, and learner participation		
Tutor Training and Incentives	Enhance tutors' competencies and sustain motivation	Provide continuous training, certification programs, and incentives such as recognition and allowances	Teachers, school heads	Php 30,000	MOOE / DepEd Funds	Quarterly SY 2026-2027	Increased teacher competence and engagement		
School Facilities and ICT Resources	Improve learning environment and access to technology	Upgrade ARAL spaces, provide devices, improve internet connectivity, and ensure sanitation facilities	School heads, LGU, stakeholders	Php 50,000	MOOE / LGU / PTA	Year-round SY 2026-2027	Improved learning environment and ICT accessibility		
Parental Involvement and Home Support	Strengthen parents' participation in learners' reading development	Conduct parent orientations, establish communication systems, and promote home-based reading activities	Teachers, parents, PTA	Php 10,000	PTA Fund	Year-round SY 2026-2027	Increased parental engagement and learner support at home		
Governance and Stakeholder Support	Improve program coordination and policy implementation	Strengthen School Governance Council involvement, build	School heads, LGU, stakeholders	Php 15,000	MOOE / External Support	Year-round SY 2026-2027	Improved coordination and program monitoring		

	tion	partnerships with LGUs and NGOs, and enhance monitoring systems							
Capacity Building and Program Sustainability	Ensure continuous and effective ARAL implementation	Conduct capacity-building programs for teaching and non-teaching personnel and regular program evaluation	Teachers, school heads, DepEd personnel	Php 10,000	MOOE / DepEd Grants	Quarterly SY 2026-2027	Sustained program improvement and effectiveness		
Strengthening Learners' Reading Skills	Improve learners' reading comprehension and fluency	Conduct guided reading sessions, remedial classes, and differentiated instruction	Teachers, learners	Php 5,000	MOOE / School Fund	Year-round SY 2026-2027	Improved reading performance and comprehension levels		
Contextualized Learning Resources	Provide reading materials suited to learners' needs	Develop reading materials with local content and comprehension activities	Teachers	Php 5,000	MOOE / School Fund	Year-round SY 2026-2027	Learner Engagement		
Intervention for Struggling Readers	Support learners with low reading achievement	Conduct diagnostic assessment to identify the learners' reading difficulties, peer tutoring for guided reading, one-on-one reading session, monitor learners' progress monthly	Teachers	Php 5,000	MOOE / School Fund	Year-round SY 2026-2027	Improvement in reading fluency and comprehension		

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